

CUSTOMER ACCESSION REPORT

COLLEGE OBSERVATORY

12/20/91

THIS REPORT PROVIDES THE CUSTOMER WITH AN ACCESSION
RECEIPT CONFIRMING ITEMS RECEIVED AND PROCESSED.
THE REPORT SORTS IN ITEM BAR CODE SEQUENCE

ITEM	IN DATE	TRAY #
C00001	12/20/91	TY35427
C00002	12/20/91	TY35430
C00003	12/20/91	TY35435
C00004	12/20/91	TY35415
C00005	12/20/91	TY35445
C00006	12/20/91	TY35482
C00007	12/20/91	TY35428
C00008	12/20/91	TY35474
C00009	12/20/91	TY35421
C00010	12/20/91	TY35429
C00011	12/20/91	TY35461
C00012	12/20/91	TY35424
C00013	12/20/91	TY35434
C00014	12/20/91	TY35432
C00015	12/20/91	TY35420
C00016	12/20/91	TY35444
C00017	12/20/91	TY35408
C00018	12/20/91	TY35423
C00019	12/20/91	TY35425
C00020	12/20/91	TY35418
C00021	12/20/91	TY35436
C00022	12/20/91	TY35433
C00023	12/20/91	TY35417
C00024	12/20/91	TY35448
C00025	12/20/91	TY35419
C00026	12/20/91	TY35479
C00027	12/20/91	TY35481
C00028	12/20/91	TY35441
C00029	12/20/91	TY35376
C00030	12/20/91	TY35437
C00031	12/20/91	TY35439
C00032	12/20/91	TY35438
C00033	12/20/91	TY35416
C00034	12/20/91	TY35478
C00035	12/20/91	TY35409
C00036	12/20/91	TY35467
C00037	12/20/91	TY35462
C00038	12/20/91	TY35453

ITEM	IN DATE	TRAY #
C00039	12/20/91	TY35471
C00040	12/20/91	TY35476
C00041	12/20/91	TY35454
C00042	12/20/91	TY35406
C00043	12/20/91	TY35475
C00044	12/20/91	TY35466
C00045	12/20/91	TY35410
C00046	12/20/91	TY35484
C00047	12/20/91	TY35450
C00048	12/20/91	TY35412
C00049	12/20/91	TY35459
C00050	12/20/91	TY35480
C00051	12/20/91	TY35464
C00052	12/20/91	TY35405
C00053	12/20/91	TY35468
C00054	12/20/91	TY35470
C00055	12/20/91	TY35401
C00056	12/20/91	TY35463
C00057	12/20/91	TY35456
C00058	12/20/91	TY35473
C00059	12/20/91	TY35472
C00060	12/20/91	TY35460
C00061	12/20/91	TY35452
C00062	12/20/91	TY35455
C00063	12/20/91	TY35465
C00064	12/20/91	TY35404
C00065	12/20/91	TY35451
C00066	12/20/91	TY35469
C00067	12/20/91	TY35403
C00068	12/20/91	TY35457
C00069	12/20/91	TY35407
C00070	12/20/91	TY35411
C00071	12/20/91	TY35477
C00072	12/20/91	TY35449
C00073	12/20/91	TY35402
C00074	12/20/91	TY35458
C00075	12/20/91	TY35414
C00076	12/20/91	TY35426
C00077	12/20/91	TY35447
C00078	12/20/91	TY35442
C00079	12/20/91	TY35422
C00080	12/20/91	TY35483
C00081	12/20/91	TY35413
C00082	12/20/91	TY35375
C00083	12/20/91	TY35431
C00085	12/20/91	TG13098
C00086	12/20/91	TG13110
C00087	12/20/91	TG13110
C00088	12/20/91	TG13098
C00089	12/20/91	TG13098
C00090	12/20/91	TG12972
C00091	12/20/91	TG13110

*for missing
CO numbers,
see next page.*

RECEIVED

NOT SHELVED

TOTAL BOOKS :
TOTAL BOXES :
TOTAL OTHER :

7
83
0

106
0
0

Total Count = 90

CUSTOMER ACCESSION REPORT

COLLEGE OBSERVATORY

12/27/91

THIS REPORT PROVIDES THE CUSTOMER WITH AN ACCESSION
RECEIPT CONFIRMING ITEMS RECEIVED AND PROCESSED.
THE REPORT SORTS IN ITEM BAR CODE SEQUENCE

ITEM	IN DATE	TRAY #
-----	-----	-----
C00084	12/27/91	TG13147
C00092	12/27/91	TG13147
C00093	12/27/91	TG13147
C00094	12/27/91	TG12986
C00095	12/27/91	TG12986
C00096	12/27/91	TG12986

RECEIVED NOT SHELVED

TOTAL BOOKS :	6	0
TOTAL BOXES :	0	0
TOTAL OTHER :	0	0

Total Count = 6

Box labels:

The bar code number coincides with
the box number, as below.

(2009) naming convention adds an extra leading 0, thus CO 0004
zero

001

001

001

1	A1	Transit Circle	11/7/1848 - 7/30/1849	
2	A2	" "	7/30/1849 - 9/25/1849	
3	A3	" "	9/26/1849 - 11/29/1849	*
4	A4	" "	11/30/1849 - 2/6/1850	
5	A5	" "	2/6/1850 - 4/30/1850	
6	A6	" "	5/1/1850 - 10/20/1850	
7	A7	" "	10/21/1850 - 12/26/1850	
8	A8	" "	12/26/1850 - 4/3/1851	*
9	A9	" "	4/3/1851 - 7/13/1851	
10	A10	" "	7/13/1851 - 9/5/1851	*
11	A11	" "	9/5/1851 - 1/15/1852	
12	A12	" "	1/15/1852 - 6/28/1852	
13	A13	" "	6/28/1852 - 12/5/1852	
14	A14	" "	12/1/1852 - 7/8/1853	
15	A15	" "	7/8/1853 - 2/26/1854	
16	A16	" "	2/28/1854 - 8/15/1854	
17	A17	" "	8/15/1854 - 11/27/1854	
18	A18	" "	11/27/1854 - 1/25/1855	
19	A19	" "	1/25/1855 - 5/6/1855	*
20	A20	" "	5/6/1855 - 7/31/1855	
21	A21	" "	8/1/1855 - 9/25/1855	
22	A22	" "	9/25/1855 - 3/27/1856	
23	A23	" "	3/27/1856 - 6/15/1856	
24	A24	" "	6/16/1856 - 9/5/1856	
25	A25	" "	9/8/1856 - 2/9/1857	
26	A26	" "	2/17/1857 - 9/21/1857	
27	A27	" "	9/21/1857 - 11/3/1857	
28	A28	" "	11/3/1857 - 2/10/1858	
29	A29	" "	2/10/1858 - 7/5/1858	
30	A30	" "	7/5/1858 - 1/24/1859	
31	A31	" "	1/24/1859 - 8/17/1859	
32	A32	" "	8/17/1859 - 1/23/1860	
33	A33	" "	1/23/1860 - 6/23/1860	
34	A34	" "	6/23/1860 - 11/29/1860	
35	A35	" "	11/29/1860 - 3/21/1861	
36	A36	" "	3/21/1861 - 10/1/1861	
37	A37	" "	10/1/1861 - 3/28/1862	
38	A38	Meridian	3/28/1862 - 5/7/1862	
39	A39	" "	5/7/1862 - 8/6/1862	

001	40	A40	Meridian Circle	8/11/1862 - 9/25/1862
	41	A41	" "	9/27/1862 - 12/8/1862
	42	A42	" "	12/10/1862 - 2/16/1863
	43	A43	" "	2/17/1863 - 5/25/1863
	44	A44	" "	5/26/1863 - 8/14/1863
002	45	A45	" "	8/14/1863 - 9/22/1863
	46	A46	" "	9/23/1863 - 12/2/1863
	47	A47	" "	12/5/1863 - 1/11/1864
	48	A48	" "	1/11/1864 - 3/3/1864
	49	A49	" "	3/7/1864 - 4/29/1864
	50	A50	" "	4/9/1864 - 5/19/1864
	51	A51	" "	5/22/1864 - 6/6/1864
	52	A52	" "	6/7/1864 - 6/19/1864
002	53	A53	" "	6/21/1864 - 7/5/1864
	54	A54	" "	7/6/1864 - 7/19/1864
	55	A55	" "	7/20/1864 - 9/9/1864
	56	A56	" "	9/10/1864 - 10/10/1864
	57	A57	" "	10/10/1864 - 11/4/1864
	58	A58	" "	11/10/1864 - 11/23/1864
	59	A59	" "	11/25/1864 - 12/20/1864
	60	A60	" "	12/30/1864 - 1/18/1865
	61	A61	" "	1/20/1865 - 2/1/1865
	62	A62	" "	2/2/1865 - 2/25/1865
002	63	A63	" "	2/27/1865 - 4/3/1865
	64	A64	" "	4/3/1865 - 4/26/1865
	65	A65	" "	5/1/1865 - 6/2/1865
	66	A66	" "	6/3/1865 - 7/4/1865
	67	A67	" "	7/5/1865 - 7/18/1865
	68	A68	" "	7/20/1865 - 8/1/1865
	69	A69	" "	8/2/1865 - 8/28/1865
	70	A70	" "	8/29/1865 - 9/15/1865
002	71	A71	" "	9/16/1865 - 9/30/1865
	72	B1	Reduction of Transits	1/1/1849 - 8/16/1849
	73	B2	" "	8/16/1849 - 12/7/1849
	74	B3	" "	12/7/1849 - 4/2/1850
	75	B4	" "	4/2/1850 - 10/5/1850
	76	B5	" "	10/5/1850 - 12/30/1850
	77	B6	" "	12/30/1850 - 4/5/1851
	78	B7	" "	4/5/1851 - 7/8/1851

~~unlabeled~~
unlabeled

002

79	B8	Reduction of Transits	7/8/1851 - 9/4/1851
80	B9	" "	9/4/1851 - 11/11/1851
81	B10	" "	11/11/1851 - 2/25/1852
82	B11	" "	2/25/1852 - 7/6/1852
83	B12	" "	7/6/1852 - 11/17/1852
84	B13	" "	11/17/1852 - 5/1/1853
85	B14	" "	5/1/1853 - 11/2/1853
86	B15	" "	11/2/1853 - 4/4/1854
87	B16	" "	4/4/1854 - 8/9/1854
88	B17	" "	8/6/1854 - 11/27/1854
89	B18	" "	11/27/1854 - 1/30/1855
90	B19	" "	1/30/1855 - 5/6/1855
91	B20	" "	5/6/1855 - 8/1/1855
92	B21	" "	7/31/1855 - 9/25/1855
93	B22	" "	9/25/1855 - 3/30/1856
94	B23	" "	3/30/1856 - 6/11/1856
95	B24	" "	6/11/1856 - 8/22/1856
96	B25	" "	8/22/1856 - 11/20/1856
97	B26	" "	11/20/1856 - 4/30/1857
98	B27	" "	4/30/1857 - 10/4/1857
99	B28	" "	10/4/1857 - 11/28/1857
100	B29	" "	11/28/1857 - 2/23/1858
101	B30	" "	2/23/1858 - 6/24/1858
102	B31	" "	6/24/1858 - 11/9/1858
103	B32	" "	11/9/1858 - 6/19/1859
104	B33	" "	6/19/1859 - 10/14/1859
105	B34	" "	10/14/1859 - 3/27/1860
106	B35	" "	3/27/1860 - 11/16/1860
107	B36	" "	11/16/1860 - 1/1/1861

003

003

003

108	C1	N. + S. Meridian Marks and Level Readings	12/5/1849 - 4/4/1853
109	C2	" " "	7/1853 - 4/21/1855
110	C3	" " "	4/21/1855 - 9/8/1856
111	C4	" " "	9/1856 - 2/24/1859
112	C5	" " "	2/24/1859 - 3/11/1862
113	C8	Instrumental Corrections	12/29/1863 - 10/1865
114	C9	Computed AR of Polar Stars	3/11/1862 - 8/19/1863
115	C10	" " "	8/22/1863 - 11/14/1864
116	C11	Chronograph Record	6/1861 - 7/1863
117	C12	" "	7/23/1863 - 11/4/1864

003

118 C13 Chronograph Record 11/10/1864 - 9/12/1865
 119 C14 " " 9/13/1865 - 2/20/1866
 120 C12 [C15] Misc. time observations
 121 D1 Minutes of Chronometer Exped. 4/1849 - 2/1850 #1 - ★
 122 E1 Meridian Circle 11/7/1859 - 5/25/1860
 123 E2 " " 5/24/1859 - 11/3/1859
 124 E3 " " 5/25/1860 - 11/13/1860
 125 E4 Declinations 12/20/1862 - 9/9/1863
 126 E5 " 9/14/1863 - 10/17/1864
 127 E6 New Transit Circle 2/17/1857 - 5/28/1858 ★
 128 E7 Transit Circle 1851 - 1853
 129 E8 " " 8/7/1851 - 12/4/1851

003

130 F1 Moon Culminations + Transits 12/1845 - 4/1846 (Comets also)
 131 F2 Comets + Meridian Transits 4/1846 - 10/1846 (Earthquake 5/12)
 132 F3 " " " 10/1846 - 4/16/1847
 133 F4 " " " 4/24/1847 - 2/9/1848
 134 F5 " " " 2/18/1848 - 8/1/1848
 135 F6 " " " 8/1/1849 - 2/27/1850 ★

003

136 F7 Meridian + Prime Vertical Obs'ns 11/6/1844 - 12/12/1844 (EARLY!)
 137 F8 West Transit 11/5/1851 - 12/16/1851
 138 F9 Prime Vertical 11/1854 - ?
 139 F10 Magnetic + Prime Vertical 1858

140 F11 Terrestrial Magnetism 3/25/1858 - 6/5/1861

004

141 F12a [Chronograph 6/8/1864 - 7/21/1864]
 142 F12b Prime Vertical Computation of Latitude 1864
 143 F13 Telegraph 7/6/1848 - 10/28/1848
 144 G1 Chronometers from July 1, 1853 - ^{7/1/1853} ~~4/21/1855~~ [Annular Eclipse 5/24/59]
 145 G2 " 7/1/1853 - 4/21/1855
 146 G3 Sidereal + Mean Time Clocks 4/21/1855 - 1/1/1856
 147 G4 " " " " 1/1/1856 - 2/27/1857
 148 G5 " " " " 2/28/1857 - 7/2/1858
 149 G6 " " " " 7/2/1856 - 7/16/1860
 150 G7 " " " " 7/14/1860 - 9/3/1862
 151 G8 " " " " 9/16/1862 - 3/2/1866

004

152 G^a Railroad Time Commenced 6/29/1854 - 10/1854
 153 G^b Trials of Pendulums + Chronometers 4/27/1857 - 2/19/1859
 154 H^a Vol I 517-604 11/1848 - 2/1849 - Comets + Double #s 1848
 155 H^a Equatorial Reductions 6/21/1860 - 1/22/1861
 156 H1 Vol I 1-80 Equatorial 10/1846 - 7/1847

004

#159
Nash
9/20/59

004

004

005

005

157	H2	Vol I	81-168
158	H3		169-256
159	H4		257-344
160	H5		345-432
161	H6		433-516
162	H7	Vol II	1-92
163	H8		93-192
164	H10		193-292
165	H11		293-392
166	H12		393-488
167	H13		489-584
168	H14	Vol III	1-98
169	H15		99-194
170	H16		195-288
171	H17		289-388
172	H18		389-484
173	H19		485-574
174	H20		575-665
175	H21		
176	H22		
177	H23		
178	H24		
179	H25		
180	H26		
181	H27		
182	H28		
183	H29		
184	H30		
185	H31		
186	H32		
187	H33		
188	H34		
189	H35		
190	H36		
191	H37		
192	H38		
193	H39		
194	H40		
195	H41		

Equatorial

"			7/1847 - 12/1847
"			12/1847 - 8/1848
"	(+prime vert.)		11/1847 - 2/1848
"	"		2/1848 - 9/1848
"	"		5/1848 - 11/1848
"			2/1849 - 6/1849
"			1/1849 - 11/1849
"			12/1849 - 1/1850
"			5/10/1850 - 9/1/1850
"			9/21/1850 - 2/25/1851
"			2/25/1851 - 12/4/1851
"			12/4/1851 - 5/18/1852
"			5/19/1852 - 10/26/1852
"			10/28/1852 - 3/10/1853
"			3/10/1853 - 4/3/1854
"			4/4/1854 - 6/13/1855
"			6/13/1855 - 4/1/1856
"			4/1/1856 - 2/15/1857
"			2/15/1857 - 5/13/1857
"			5/13/1857 - 9/1/1857
"			8/23/1857 - 10/22/1857
"			10/23/1857 - 12/14/1857
"			12/15/1857 - 3/17/1858
"			3/18/1858 - 7/13/1858
"			7/14/1858 - 9/25/1858
"			9/25/1858 - 11/11/1858
"			11/11/1858 - 5/4/1859
"			5/4/1859 - 10/26/1859
"			10/26/1859 - 1/31/1860
"			1/31/1860 - 3/14/1860
"			3/15/1860 - 3/29/1860
"			3/30/1860 - 5/2/1860
"			5/2/1860 - 6/22/1860
"			6/24/1860 - 7/4/1860
"			7/4/1860 - 9/22/1860
"			9/26/1860 - 1/30/1861
"			1/31/1861 - 4/8/1861
"			4/9/1861 - 5/2/1861
"			5/3/1861 - 6/22/1861

Daguerre type
★

Last obs. of
W.C.B.

005

005

006

196 H42
 197 H43
 198 H44
 199 H45
 200 H46
 201 H47
 202 H48
 203 H49
 204 H50
 205 H51
 206 H52
 207 H53
 208 H54
 209 H55
 210 H56
 211 K1
 212 K2
 213 K3
 214 K4
 215 K5
 216 K6
 217 K7
 218 K8
 219 K9
 220 K10
 221 K11
 222 K12
 223 K13
 224 K14
 225 K15
 226 K16
 227 K17
 228 K18
 229 K19
 230 K20
 231 K21
 232 K22
 233 K23
 234 K24

Equatorial

Zones

6/22/1861 - 7/13/1861
 7/13/1861 - 9/12/1861
 9/16/1861 - 12/30/1861
 1/1/1862 - 4/18/1862
 4/19/1862 - 7/5/1862
 7/6/1862 - 8/19/1862
 8/19/1862 - 12/2/1862
 12/6/1862 - 4/9/1863
 4/13/1863 - 6/4/1863
 6/10/1863 - 10/1/1863
 10/5/1863 - 2/19/1864
 2/19/1863 - 3/21/1864
 3/21/1864 - 6/1864
 6/1864 - 3/29/1865
 4/3/1865 - 2/5/1866
 4/7/1852 - 5/4/1852
 5/4/1852 - 11/3/1852
 11/4/1852 - 12/14/1852
 12/15/1852 - 1/8/1853
 1/11/1853 - 2/11/1853
 2/12/1853 - 3/15/1853
 3/16/1853 - 4/1/1853
 4/8/1853 - 5/11/1853
 5/31/1853 - 9/8/1853
 9/27/1854 - 12/8/1854
 12/8/1854 - 2/3/1855
 2/12/1855 - 4/16/1855
 4/23/1855 - 7/17/1855
 3/30/1859 - 5/3/1859
 5/3/1859 - 5/14/1859
 5/23/1859 - 8/25/1859
 8/29/1859 - 11/26/1859
 11/26/1859 - 2/17/1860
 2/21/1860 - 11/24/1860
 11/20/1860 - 2/4/1861
 2/26/1860 - 4/8/1861
 4/8/1861 - 6/25/1861
 7/11/1861 - 10/29/1861
 9/24/1861 - 1/31/1862

See 284 for more

Catalog #'s

006

235	K25	Zones	10/22/1862 - 2/10/1863	
236	K26	"	2/18/1862 - 5/1864	
237	K27	"	6/23/1864 - [9/27/1864]	
238	L1	Reduction of Zone Observations	1853	Explanation
239	K28	Zones	10/5/1864 - 12/1/1864	
240	L2	Reduction of Zone Observations	1853	
241	L3	" " "	1853	
242	L4	" " "	1853	
243	L5	" " "	1853	
244	L6	" " "	1853	
245	L7	" " "	1853	
246	L8	" " "		

006

247	L9	[Comparisons of Zones]		
248	L10	Reductions of Zones No Reductions	1859	
249	L11	Reductions of Zones Comparison of Magnitudes	1859	
250	L12	Special Zones and Magnitudes		
251	L13	Revision of Zones. Magnitudes		
252	M2	Reduction of Zones - I		
253	M3	Gould's Universal Index (Catalog?)		
254	M5	[Tables, Procedures]		

006

255	M4	Table of Contents of Various Books containing Reads of Observ ^{ions} 1841-1855		
256	M7	Various Memoranda [Longitude determination, mag. meas., etc.] 1844-5		
257	M9	Catalog Stars 1854-58		
258	M10	Tables for Appointing Instrumental Corrections [c. 1855]		
259	M11	Catalogue of Stars for Zones [c. 1853]		
260	M12	Reduction of Stars in Weisse (?) from 0° to 1° N to 1853		
261	M13	Printing of Zone Obsns 1854 + History + Description of the Obs.		

007

262	M14	Lists of persons + institutions recipients of H. Annals		
263	M15	Meteorological 1/1/1861 - 5/1863		
264	M16	1859-60 Comet Seeker 12/1/1859 - 9/11/1860		
265	M17	Colorado Survey - Time 12/23/1857 - 5/23/1858		
266	M18	" " Latitude by Polaris 12/23/1857 - 5/23/1858		
267	M19	[Solar Observations] " 1/5/1855 - 5/2/1855		
268	M20	[Catalog of Bright Nebulae + Clusters] 6/16/1850 - 5/1853		
269	M21	[Comet Seeking] 6/10/1847 - 6/5/1850		
270	M23	Books Received at the Obs. of Harw. Coll. 1862-1878		
271	M24	Reductions of Moon Culminations 1/1849 - 5/28/1852		
272	M25	" " " 7/1851 - 10/2/1854		
273	M26	P. S. N. [drawings of * config's and angle.] 8/16/1856 - 7/4/1856		

	274	M27	[11/15/1850 - 8/22/1851]	
	275	M28	Gould's Universal Index	
007	276	M29	Printing 1860-1863	
	277	M30	Memoranda for Obs. Report	1/7/1861 - 12/31/1864
	278	M31	Memoranda	1/3/1862 - 1/2/1865
	279	M32	Catalog of Books in the Phillips Library, commenced	10/9/1856
	280	M33	Chronometer - Stars	1862-5
	281	M34	Transit Catalog	
	282	M35	Eclipse of 4/25/1846 - Portland	
	283	M36	Account of Various Records + Papers belonging to the Obs	- 1866
	284	N1	Equatorial	6/9/1866 - 7/6/1866
007	285	N2	"	7/9/1866 - 7/22/1866
	286	N3	"	7/24/1866 - 8/11/1866
	287	N4	"	8/13/1866 - 8/25/1866
	288	N5	"	8/26/1866 - 9/10/1866
	289	N6	"	9/12/1866 - 10/2/1866
	290	N7	"	10/2/1866 - 10/21/1866
	291	N8	"	10/22/1866 - 1/19/1867
	292	N9	"	1/23/1867 - 4/23/1867
007	293	N10	"	4/25/1867 - 10/24/1867
	294	N11	"	10/25/1867 - 1/16/1868
	295	N12	"	1/27/1868 - 4/1/1868
	296	N13	"	4/1/1868 - 10/9/1868 [Spectra]
008	297	N14	"	10/10/1868 - 12/19/1868
	298	N15	"	12/22/1868 - 4/22/1869
	299	N16	"	4/28/1869 - 10/18/1869
	300	N17	"	10/19/1869 - 5/17/1870
	301	N18	" Misc. Obsns	10/31/1871 - 11/27/1872
	302	N19	" " "	12/24/1869 - 9/2/1874
	303	N20	"	12/8/1874 - 7/11/1875
	304	N21	Asteroids	7/13/1870 - 12/21/1870
	305	N22	"	2/13/1871 - 8/10/1871
	306	N23	" (W.A. Rogers)	
	307	N24	"	
008	308	N25	Reduction of Asteroid Obsns	1870
	309	N26	" " "	1870-71
	310	N27	Reduction to app. places of some stars used in 1870	
	311	N28	" " " " " "	
	312	N29	Reduction of Asteroid Obsns	1870

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313	N30		Search for Asteroids	1870
314	N31		Equatorial - Obsns of Asteroids + comets (copy)	
315	N32		Computation of app. place, differ. refract., Equatorial Comp 2	6/30/1866 - 4/26/1866
316	N33		Reductions of Equatorial Obsns	10/15/1874 - 6/2/1875
317	N34	v.1	Equatorial (copy)	4/9/1866 - 8/26/1866
318	N35	v.2	"	8/27/1866 - 10/20/1866
319	N36	v.3	"	10/21/1866 - 1/14/1867
320	N37	v.4	"	1/14/1867 - 4/26/1867
321	N38	v.5	"	4/26/1867 - 10/19/1867
322	N39	v.6	"	10/22/1867 - 2/1/1868
323	N40	v.7	"	2/3/1868 - 6/28/1868
324	N41		Catalog of Nebulae (G.M. Searle)	
325	N42		Measurement of photogr of eclipses	1869-1870
326	N43		" " " Solar "	1870
327	N44	vol I	Notes to sketches of sun by L. Trouvelot	10/30/1870 - 4/13/1873
328	N45	vol II	" " " " "	4/14/1873 - 9/30/1874
329	N46		Solar photography (Woolbach plates)	7/40/1870 - 11/30/1876
329a	N48		General record of Work	1869-1872
330	N50		Tables, etc.	1866-67
331	N51		Reduced Measures of Double Stars - E. Equatorial	1866-1867
332	O 1		East Transit Observation	5/1/1866 - 9/2/1866
333	O 2		" " "	9/4/1866 - 5/24/1867
334	O 3		" " "	5/31/1867 - 11/5/1867
335	O 4		" " "	11/9/1867 - 7/10/1868
336	O 5		" " "	7/16/1868 - 10/2/1868
337	O 6		" " (Time)	10/3/1868 - 8/22/1869
338	O 7		" " "	8/29/1869 - 6/6/1870
339	O 8		" " (Occultations)	6/12/1870 - 1/27/1871
340	O 9		" " (Time)	12/1/1871 - 12/27/1871
341	O 10		Chronograph Record	4/2/1866 - 7/29/1869
342	O 11		East Transit (Errors)	4/17/1866 - 9/17/1867
343	O 12		Longitude Campaign: Cambridge - Washington	1867
344	O 13		Transit Observations 1867	6/28/1867 - 6/29/1867
345	O 14		Formulae for Reduction of Transit Observations + Tables	~1867
346	[O 15]		Chronograph Record	7/31/1867 - 12/19/1867
347	O 16		"	12/19/1867 - 8/14/1868
348	O 17		"	8/14/1868 - 7/30/1869
349	O 18		"	8/13/1869 - 7/7/1870
350	O 19		Record of Errors of Clocks	1866 - 1869

Almost nothing in this book

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351	[020 ²]	Stars to be Observed w/ East Transit	1868-1870
352	020	Second Computation of Instrument Errors.	1867-1868
353	021	Longitude Computations from Coast Survey	1869
354	022	[Transit Observations]	8/24/1870 - 10/23/1870
355	023	Longitude - Field Reductions	1871
356	024	Clock Corrections	1869-1872
357	025	" "	1872-1875
358	026	" "	1875
359	027	Notes on Astron Engravings, Spanish Weather record, Phillips Fund	
360	028	Eclipse of 1869. Reports	[Beautiful volume]
361	029	Personal equation observations	1871
362	P1	Magnetic Observations	8/16/1866 - 2/17/1868
363	P2	Meteorological Observations	1866
364	P3	" " (?)	1866
365	P4	Daily Journal [meteorological]	1867
366	P5	" "	1868
367	P6	" "	1869
368	P7	" "	1870
369	P8	" "	1871 ("Clayton's Octavo Diary")
370	P9	" "	1872
371	P10	" "	1873
372	P11	" "	1874
373	P12	" "	1875
374	P13	" "	1876
375	P14	" "	1877
376	P15	" "	1878
377	P16	" "	1879
378	Q1	Meteorological Record	1866, 1867, 1868
379	Q2	" " of HCO	1869
380	Q3	" " "	1870, 1871
381	Q4	" " "	1872-1877
382	Q5	" " "	1878-1879, July-Dec 1866
383		Mr. J.G. Home's Original Minutes of Chronometer Expedition	1857
384		A — A — of the White Mts. of New Hampshire	1853 (N.B. Annular Eclipse 1851)
385		[Paris to Cambridge Telegraph]	6/20-7/12 ~1861?
386		U.S. Coast Survey, Benj. Pierce, Supdt: Letter book + Abstract - Long Party	1868
387		Observations and Longitude Computations	1872 (U.S. Coast Survey)
388		Longitude + latitude No. 1 (Bolivia)	1892-93
389		Time Service	4/18/1880 - 4/19/1881

390		Meridian Circle Record - Mr. Austin	8/16/1870 - 5/13/1871
391	Vol 1	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Peirce	3/6/1872 - 3/21/1872
392	2	"	" " 3/22/1872 - 6/5/1872
393	3	"	" " 6/6/1872 - 7/2/1872
394	4	"	" " 5/4/1872 - 5/30/1872 Dup
395	5	"	" " 5/31/1872 - 6/13/1872
396	6	"	" " 6/10/1872 - 6/30/1872
397	7	"	" " 6/30/1872 - 7/30/1872
398	8	"	" " 7/30/1872 - 8/9/1872
399	9	"	" " 8/9/1872 - 9/15/1872
400	10	"	" " 8/18/1872 - 3/7/1873
401	11	"	" " 3/9/1873 - 6/7/1873
402	12	"	" " 6/8/1873 - 7/1/1873
403	13	"	" " 9/6/1873 - 9/22/1873
404	14	"	" " 9/22/1873 - 9/30/1873
405	15	"	" " 9/30/1873 - 10/11/1873
406	16	"	" " 10/11/1873 - 2/10/1874
407	18	"	" " 4/13/1874 - 5/3/1874
408	19	"	" " 5/20/1874 - 7/15/1874
409	20	"	" " 7/17/1874 - 8/2/1874
410	21	"	" " 8/3/1874 - 8/4/1874
411	22	"	" " 8/22/1874 - 11/26/1874
412	23	"	" " 11/26/1874 - 12/21/1874
413	24	"	" " 12/21/1874 - 1/14/1875
414	25	"	" " 5/28/1872
415	[paper folder]	Index to books on Meridian Circle Work	1870-1886
416		Fundamental Stars for Zones B8	3/17/1873 - 12/1/1873
417		General Catalog. Obsns + Reductions B1	1871-72
418		Fundamental Stars. Obsns + Reductions. Final Values B1	1870-71
419		Mars. Mars Comparison Stars. ARIADNE Comp. Stars	1877
420		Flexure Constants. Equator Point Corrections	1874-75
421		Instrumental Constants 1870-71, depending on new Pulikowa Place	
422		Barometer. Thermometer Runs. Collimation. Flexure	1870-79
423		Refraction Constants. B + T + S	1870-86
424		Obsns. w/ Meridian Circle on 2 mes 50° to 55°	11/16/1870 - 12/16/1870
425		" " " " " "	12/16/1870 - 5/28/1871
426		Misc. Tables. Formulae for Zone Reductions	1870-71
427		Misc. Obsns. Transit of Venus. Longitude Montreal - Cambridge	1883
428		Obsns of Tempel's Comet 1873, Asteroids 1873, Periodicity of Kuling Machine	1877

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Ruling Machine Screws; Discovery of (112) and (109) + ephemerides
Asteroid 109 - Elements + Ephemeris 1877-78
Orbit of 109, 112 1871-74
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Planetary Positions (Heliocentric) 1750-1860
Step? lists (Zones)

Chronograph Record 5/27/1880 - 10/5/1880

A.G.? Absolute Work Star List - Final List of Dates of Obsns. 1879-81 John A. Dunne
Rogers' Work " " Meridian Circle Obsns. 1879-81 Anna Winlock
" " Notebook 1898-1907 Selma C. Bond

A.G. Posting Book 1897-1908
Rogers' Abs. Work - notebook 1904-1911 John A. Dunne

Special Light Curves with Photometer 1895-96

[Variable Stars ~ 1897]

Ephemerides of Variable Stars 1896-98

Measurement of Comp. Stars for Variable w/Photometer 1895-1901

[Variable Stars] ~ 1897-98

I Obsns of Variable Stars 1890-91 W^m Maxwell Reed
II " " " 1891-
III " " " 1891-92 "
IV " " " 1892 "
V " " " 1892-93 "
451 VII " " " 1894-95 "
452 VI " " " 1893-94 "
453 VIII " " " 1896-98 "
454 IX " " " 1898-1900 "
455 " " " 1900 "

Notebook of Visual Observations - SS Cyg, Nova Per 1899-1902 H.R. Colson, Jr

West Equatorial Observations 4/10/1898-5/12/1899 [SS Cyg]

Equatorial Work [Recond of 72 books]

Index - Also lists of Variables, etc.

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Rutherford Millimeter Plate Measurements, etc. 8/16/1897-7/25/1898

Meteorological Observations, etc. 6/23/1880-8/20/1885

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Aug - Oct 1877

α Ceti, λ Cyg, δ —, β Persei 1838-1854

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Photometer Reductions 1877

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468	R25		Ephemerides of Saturn's and Jupiter's Satellites		
469	R26		Errors of Circles, Misc. Obsns - W. Equatorial	1877-78	
470	R28		Misc Obsns. and Reductions	c 1878	
471	R29		[Summary of Variable Stars]	1840-1862	
472	R30	5	Photometric Observations	1877	
473	R31	6	" "	1878	
474	R32		c 1878		
013 475	R33		Observations + Lists	1879-81	ECP?
476	R34		Form for Eq. Observations	1879	↓
477	R35		Prospective Work + Proposed Form of Publication - W. Equatorial	1874-81	
478	R43	7		1878	
479	R44	8		1878	
480	R45	14		1879	
481	R46		Photometric Obsns with W. Equatorial	1878-79	
482			" "	"	
483			Description of Procedures + Opt. Setups		
484			" " + Other Obsns	1879	
485			" " " "	1879-80	
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488			Eclipses of Jupiter Satellites	1878-79	
489			Eye + Photom Estimates of Standard Magn	1881	J.R. Edmund
490			Comet Reductions #1	1881	
491			" " #2	1880-83	
492		26		1881-82	
493		28		1882	
494			6 1/4 "	1882-83	
495			15" (?)	1884	
496			Comets	1882-88	
497			"	1882-85	
498			"	1883-87	
499			15" (?) Equatorial	1885	
500			Comets	1882-89	
014 501			"	1882-94	
502			"	1883-87	
015 503			"	1885-88	
504			"	1888-89	
505			" Copies of telegrams	1889-98	
506			" (10)	1890	

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 Variable Stars (Arequipa)
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 Telescope Mechanical Notes + Golf Scores
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R.W. Clifford
 Andrew E. Douglass
 Andrew S. Douglass
 Wm B Clymer
 Wm B Clymer
 various
 A.J. Cannon?
 A.J. Cannon I
 Chas. P. Howard
 A.J. Cannon II
 S.I. Bailey
 " "
 A.J. Cannon

See KG 136
 712
 + preceding

129, 125 are
w. KG 1366.374
and .375

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notebook # 2

Use these
15" record books??

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H.R. Colson

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15-inch record books?

15" record

15" Equatorial

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624	200	15" Equatorial	1918
625	201	" "	1918
626	202	" "	1918-19
627	203	" "	1919-20
628	204	" "	1920-23
629	205	" "	1926-27
630	206	" "	1928-30
631	207	" "	1934-35
632	208	" "	1935-36
633	209	" "	1936
634	210	" "	1936
635	211	" " (also 12" record)	1936-39
636	212	" "	1936-37
637	1	12-in. Equatorial	1914
638		" "	1915-16
639		" "	1916-17
640		" "	1917-18
641		" "	1919
642	[Box of Papers] II Matens (Leonids) 1898-99 Arizuka Obs.		
643	12-in Equatorial	- Variable Star Obsns	1919-20
644	"	" " " "	1920
645	"	" " " "	1920-21
646	"	" " " "	1921
647	"	" " " "	1921
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649	"	" " " "	1921-22
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658	"	" " " "	1925
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660	"	" " " "	1925-26
661	"	" " " "	1926-27
662	"	" " " "	1927

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		12-in Equatorial - Variable Star Obsns	1927-28	
		" " " " "	1928-29	
		" " " " "	1928-33	
		" " " " "	1934-35	
		" " " " "	1935-36	
1		[24" Clark Refractor?]	1905-06	[Leon Campbell?]
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6			1909	
7			1909	
8			1909-10	
9			1910-11	
1		Photometric Observations	1872	C.S. Pierce
2		" "	1872	" "
3		" "	1872	" "
4		" "	1873	" "
5		" "	1873	" "
6		" "	1874	" "
7		" "	1874	" "
8		" "	1874-75	" "
		Experiments with Photometer	1872	C.S. Pierce
		η Centauri Spectral Study	1911	Leah B. Allen
1		Clusters - Spectrophotometric facings	c1930	Carol Jane Arger
2		α Cyg, Vega	1930-36?	" " "
3		" "	"	" " "
4		h Per, NGC 663	"	" " "
5		Clusters	c1932+	" " "
6		Clusters	1934	" " "
1		Misc; Variables	1918-19	Mary ^D Applegate
2		Variables, Map of the Sky	1918-19	" "
4		Map of the Sky, Sequences for Orion Neb.	1919	" "
5		Asteroids + Novae	1919-20	" "
6		Novae + Variables	1920-21	" "
7		Map of the Sky	1920-21	" "
		Daily Journal (13" - Peru)	1889-90	S.I. Bailey
25		Double Stars; Planets	1894-96	" "
1		Misc.; Variables	1917-19	Dorothy W. Block
2		Spectrum Work	1917-19	" "

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702	3	o Ceti, Nova Aql 3	1917-19	Dorothy W. Bloch
703	4	Variables	1918-19	" " "
704	6	Asteroids	1918-19	" " "
705	7	Variables	1919	" " "
706	1	Variable Stars + Meteors	1903	F.E. Brasch
707	1	Variable Stars	1896-98	S.E. Breslin
708	2	" "	1898	" "
709	3	" "	1898	" "
710	4	" "	1899	" "
711	5	" "	1901-02	" "
712	6	" "	1902	" "
713	7	" "	1902-03	" "
714	8	" "	1903	" "
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718	12	" "	1903-04	" "
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724	18	" "	1904-05	" "
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733	27	" "	1907	" "
734	28	" "	1907	" "
735	29	" "	1907	" "
736	30	" "	1907-08	" "
737	[31]	" "	1908	" "
738	32	" "	1908	" "
739	33	" "	1909	" "
740	34	" "	1909-10	" "

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Visual Observations	1902-03	
	1903-04	
	1904	
	1904-05	
	1905-09	
	1906-07	
	1907-09	Annie J. Cannon
Notes for Reading	1911-39	" " "
Guest Book	1912-35	" " "
Variable Stars, Longitude Determination	1862-82	Seth C. Chandler 1897 " "
W Virginis I	1916	C.A. Chant
λ of Sp. lines in red region of stars	1926-27	C.T. Chase
Spectra of Novae	1926	Paul Dardovich
Journal - lat. + Long. Work	1896	Andrew E. Dingle
Radiometric Book I	1937-38	
Radiometry II	1939-40	Ed. Berson
" Program Bk I	1936-38	" "
Galvanometry Book I	1937-38	
Variable Stars	1890-92	W.P. Fleming
" "	1892-94	" "
" " ; Spectra	1892-94	" "
" "	1893-98	" "
" "	1894-95	" "
" " ; Spectra	1895-99	" "
" "	1895-96	" "
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" "	1898-1903	" "
" "	1898-1905	" "
" "	1899-1905	" "
" " ; Comp. Spectra	1903-07	" "
" " " "	1903-10	" "
" " ; Photometer	1905-08	" "
Novae, Comets, Spectra	1906-11	" "
Sp. Class; Misc Obsns.	1908-11	" "

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missing 11/1991

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ledger of LPV's 000339 - 095659 spectra
" " 100661 - 185905 "
" " 190048 - 235939 "
Cluster and Faint Stars 1904 - ~11 "
Nova Perseus Reductions 1902 "
Variable Stars "
Measurements of Bright Line Spectra 1890 "
Reductions of Photographic Observations 1886-87
" " " 1886-87
" " " 1886
" " " 1886
" " " 1886-87
" " " -
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" " " 1887
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" " " 1887
" " " 1887-88
" " " 1887
" " " 1887-89
" " " "
Catalog of E. stars
Description of Spectra 1887-88
" " " 1887-89
Catalog of E. Stars
" " "
Discordant Spectra; Remarks on Rejected Measures
G Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates
E " " " "
Description of Spectra
G Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates
Description of Spectra
C Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates
Catalog of I plates

W.P. Fleming
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These may all be WPF?

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35 Reductions of Photographs Observations 1888-90
 36 F+G Discordant Spectra
 39 Reduction of Photographs Observations
 40 Catalog of Plates Classes N, H, L; Peruvian Plates ~1889
 41 " " " C, D " " ~1889
 42 Objects of Interest on Spectrum Plates ~1889
 45 " " " " " " ~1890
 97 " " So. Bache Plates 1898-1907 W.P. Fleming
 49 Miscellaneous (Ecl., Solar, etc) 1890-91
 50 Discussion of Draper Catalog
 51 Measurement of Spectrum Plates - So. Draper Cat. 1890-92
 [52] Description of Spectrum Measures " " " 1890-93
 53 Discussion of Draper Catalog
 56 " " " "
 57 Catalog of Chart Plates (I - 8")
 58 " " " "
 59 " " " (B in Peru)
 61 1892
 62 1892-93
 63 1893
 64 1893
 65 1893
 67 1893
 68 1893
 69 1893-94
 70 1894-1903
 Description of Spectra Measures - So. Draper Cat. ~~B~~
 Spectra class C
 Description of Spectra Measures - So. Draper Cat 1894-1904
 Spectra to be confirmed in cat. of III Stars
 " " " " " "
 Stellar Parallax Stars (13")
 Spectra to be confirmed in cat. of III stars
 Constants in South Draper Catalog
 Reduction of Plates Having less than 4 Std. Stars.
 (15) Not on Draper Cat; Accounts of Share-Holders of the Camera 5/1892
 81 Measures of Spect. Plates (South Draper Cat) 1903-04
 82 " " " " " " 1903
 83 " " " " " " 1903-04

all WPF?

22.866

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missing 11/12/91

898	96	Objects of Interest - Bruce Spectrum Plates	1896-1909	
899	98	" " - Northern	1898-1911	
900	99	" " - So. Bache Plates	1907-1911	W.P. Fleming
901	1	Variables + Halley's Comet		W.S. Frank
902		Colors of 2149 Southern Stars		" "
903	1	Variables		B.P. Gerasimovic
904	2	"	1912-29	"
905	3	"	1900-20	"
906	4	"	1899-1927	"
907	5	Spectrophotometry of B + O Stars		"
908	6	New Variables	1899-1919	"
909	7	Color Indices of long Period Variables		"
910	8	Spectrophotometry of B + Wolf-Rayet stars		"
911	9	Variable Stars	1900-27	"
912		B Star Observations	1902	Mauds E. Harrison
913		MC plates taken for Standard Magnitude	1908	" "
914		Measurement of Variable Stars	1908	Margaret Harwood
915		" widths of A + B Stars	1922	Marian A. Hawes
916	4	Assorted Plate measurements	1912-18	" "
917		5-in. Equatorial	1918	" "
918	1	Variable Stars	1904-06	{ Anson S. Lear Guy Hill
919		Variable Star Observations	1889-1916	E.H. ?
920		Color correction for tel. objectives	1898	Charles P. Howard
921		Assorted Plate measurements		L. Hofraeger
922		" " "	1928-30	"
923	1	Measurements of Plates, Stars, etc.	1895-98	Edward S. King
924	2	Reductions of Measures	1899-	" "
925	3	Notes: Photographic Instruments	1904-24	" "
926	3	Measurements: Distances, Altitudes, Plates	1901-02	" "
927	4	Assorted Plate Measurements	1902	" "
928	5	Color distance measurements	1920	" "
929	6	Schilt Photometry	1927-28	" "
930		Photographic Measurement of Light	1897	
931		Computation Book No. 2	1916	Edward S. King
932	1	Photographic Magnitudes, Misc	1914-18	Henrietta S. Leavitt
933	2	Variables, Observations	1902-03	" "
934	4	Examination of Plates	1903	" "
935	5	Variables	1903	" "
936		Phoebe	1904	" "

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937	1	th Circumpolar Variables	1895-96	Henrietta S. Laint
938	2	Variable Star Observations	1896	" "
939	3	" " " + Plate measures	1896	" "
940	4	" " " " "	1896	" "
941	5	" " " " "	1902	" "
942	6	Circumpolar Variables	1902-04	" "
943	7	Variable Star Observations	1904	" "
944	8	Miscellaneous Observations	1904-10	" "
945	13	" "	1906-16	" "
946	22	Discovery of New Variables	1907-08	" "
947	23	Comparison Stars	1906-07	" "
948	24	Observations of New Variables	1906-07	" "
949	25	" " "	1907-14	" "
950	26	Std. Photog. Magnitudes - T'plates	1907-09	" "
951	27	" " "	1908-10	" "
952	28	" Magnitudes	1909-14	" "
953	29	Std. Photog. Magnitudes - South Pole	1910-12	" "
954	30	" " "	1910	" "
955	32	" " "	1911-14	" "
956	33	Miscellaneous Journal	1911-12	" "
957	34	Miscellaneous	1911-14	" "
958	35	Objects looked up by Request	1914-18	" "
959	36	Standard Magnitudes	1914-19	" "
960	37	Miscellaneous - Comp. Stars	1914-16	" "
961	38	Catalogs (Comparison Stars)	1915-19	" "
962	39	Miscellaneous (Variables)	1915-19	" "
963	40	Discovery of New Variables	1916-20	" "
964	41	Miscellaneous (esp. Novae)	1916-20	" "
965	43	Standard Magnitudes	1919-21	" "
966	44	Miscellaneous (Variables ^{incl. RV Sgr. 1905})	1920-21	" "
967	1	Miscellaneous Observations - Variables	1893-96	Evelyn F. Leland
968	2	" " " MS	1896	" "
969	3	" " " MS	1896	" "
970	4	" " " MS	1896-97	" "
971	5	" " " MS	1897-98	" "
972	7	" " " WGen	1897-98	" "
973	15	Measures of Eros (South Pole)	1899-1902	" "
974	16	" NewSat. (Phoebe) of Saturn, Nova Sgr	1899-1906	" "
975	25	Measures of M3, etc.	1902-03	" "

	976	26	Measures of Eos	1902-04	Evelyn F. Keland
	977	27	Search for variables; measures	1902-03	" "
	978	28	" " "	1903-04	" "
See 11366.007	979	30	" " "	1904-07	" "
	980	31 & 32	" " "	1907-09	" "
	981	33	" " "	1904-10	" "
	982	34	Scale Measures (2p. instruction of ECP)	1907-10	" "
	983	37	" " "	1911-12	" "
	984	35	" " "	1910-12	" "
038	985	36	" " "	1910-11	" "
	986	38	" " "	1912	" "
	987	39	" " "	1913-14	" "
	988	40	Series Reductions	1913	" "
	989	41	Observing Book - MS	1913	" "
039	990	42	Series Reductions	1913	" "
	991	43	" " "	1913-14	" "
	992	44	" " and MS Variables	1914-15	" "
	993	45	" " "	1913-14	" "
	994	46	" " "	1913-15	" "
	995	47	" " "	1914-15	" "
	996	48	" " "	1914-15	" "
	997	49	" " "	1915-17	" "
	998	50	" " "	1915-17	" "
	999	51	" " "	1915-17	" "
11366	.000	53	Measures of Variables in MS	1917	" "
	.001	52	" " "	1916-17	" "
	002	54	" " "	1917-18	" "
	003	55	" " "	1917-18	" "
039	004	56	Observing Book	1918-	" "
	005	57	" " "	1918	" "
	006	58	Long Exposure H.S. Regions + Series	1918-19	" "
	007	29	New Satellite of Saturn + N. Polar Seg.	1904-11	" "
	008	59	M Determinations - North Pole Plates	1918-19	" "
	009	60	" " " " "	1919-	" "
	010	61	" " " " "	1919-20	" "
	011	62	" " " " "	1919-20	" "
	012	63	" " " " "	1920	" "
	013	64	MF Series	1920	" "
040	014	65	" " "	1920-21	" "

	015	66	MF Series	1921	Evelyn F. Ireland
	016	67	MC and A Plates	1921	" "
040	017	68	Large Magellanic Cloud	1921-22	" "
	018	1	MC Plates	1915-16	H.S. Locke
	019	2	" "	1915-16	" "
	020	3	" "	1916	" "
	021	4	" "	1916, 18	" "
	022	5	" "	1916-17	" "
	023	6	" "	1917	" "
	024	7	Misc. Plates (AC, etc.)	1917-18	" "
040	025	8	MC Plates	1917-18	" "
	026	9	" "	1917-18	" "
	027	10	B and MC Plates	1917-19	" "
	028	1	Observing Book	1910-19	J.C.M. → Johnanna C.S. Mack
	029	2	" " (Scale Measures)	1913-18	" "
041	030	3	" " (MD Plates)	1913-19	" "
	031	5	" " (Misc. Plates)	1918-19	" "
	032	7	B Series	1919	" "
	033	8	Observing Book (B Series)	1919	" also Mackie?"
	034	9	" " (Misc. Measures)	1919-20	M.K.?
	035	10	Novae? (Maps of Sky, AC Plates)	1919-20	" "
	036	1	Observing Book - Variable Stars, etc.	1912-13	Genevieve F. Mattheu
	037	2	" " Scale Measures	1913	" "
	038	3	" " Series Measures	1913-16	" "
	039	4	" " Series, etc.	1914	" "
	040	5	" " Miscellaneous	1914-15	" "
	041	7	Circumpolar Variables	1914-15	" "
	042	8	" " (Est. of Mag.)	1914-15	" "
	043	9	Series Measures (Principally blue plates)	1915	" "
	044	10	" " (" yellow ")	1915-16	" "
041	045	6	Circumpolar Variables	1914-16	" "
	046	11	" " (Est. of brightness)	1915-16	" "
	047	12	" " (overflow)	1915	" "
	048	13	" " "	1916	" "
	049	14	" " (Record of Obs. on Photo's)	1916	" "
042	050		Tables of Ursa Majoris	1894-96	Antonia C. Maury
missing 11/1991	051		Rotation of Primary Star + Separation of Satellites	1928-32	" "
	052		Formulae for Reduction, Phase in HA & J	1918-22	" "
missing 11/1991	053		(Loose Papers) β Lyrae + others	1933	" "

	054	1	Obs. Book, Meas. of Variables + Standard Sq.	1912	Mollie E. O'Reilly
	055	2	Misc Observations, Variables, Etc.	1914-17	" "
042	056	3	Scale Meas. of Std. Regions on I series	1913-14	" "
	057	4	Circumpolar Variables - Meas. of Comp Stars	1914	" "
	058	5	MC Plates	1914	" "
	059	6	Meas. of Misc. Plates	1914	" "
	060	7	" " "	1914	" "
	061	8	MC + Misc. Plates	1914	" "
	062	9	" " "	1914	" "
	063	10	" " "	1914-15	" "
	064	11	" " "	1914-15	" "
042	065	12	" " "	1915-17	" "
	066	13	" " "	1915	" "
→	067	14	" " "	1915	" "
	068	15	" " "	1915	" "
	069	16	" " "	1915	" "
043	070	17	" " "	1915-16	" "
	071	18	Southern and AS plates	1915-16	" "
	072	19	MC and Misc. Plates	1916-17	" "
	073	20	Miscellaneous	1916-17	" "
	074	21	Obs. Book —	1916-17	" "
	075	22	Southern plates	1916	" "
	076	23	Mostly southern regions	1916	" "
	077	24	" " "	1916-17	" "
	078	25	" " "	1917	" "
	079	26	" " "	1917	" "
	080	27	Miscellaneous	1917-18	" "
	081	28	"	1917-18	" "
	082	29	Obs. book	1918	" " Sloan
	083	30	Scale Measures	1918	" " "
	084	31	B series	1918	" " "
043	085	32	Cat. Sc. Measures	1918	" " "
	086	33	For Cat. 1° Square	1918	" " "
→	087	34	Cat 4° Square	1918	" " "
	088	1	8" Polar Equatorial	1910-13	Philip G. O'Reilly
	089	2	" " "	1912-13	" "
44	090	3	" " " (Variables)	1913	" "
	091	1	Various Plate Measures		Cecilia H. Payne
	092	2	" " "		" "

Cecilia H. Payne

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Various Plate Measures
" " "
Wavelength Calculations
Apertured MC plates
Emission Lines, Apertured Spectra
Apertured Arcturus, Vega
Microphotometer, General
Apertured Altair, Betelgeuse
Apertured c Stars + Others
Single Spectra (Capella, Rigel, Sirius, Altair)

c.1926?

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102 12
103 13

Apertured β Cas
General Ledgers
Line Photometry

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107 17
108 18

Gaertner
Line Photometry
Plates

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109 20
110 22
111 24
112 25
113 26

Apertured Mira, α Cyg, α Per
Pleiades Background
Mira, ξ UMa Summary
K Stars

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114 27
115 28
116 29

Angstrom Magnitudes
Schilt Microphotometer
C-stars
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117 30
118 31
119 32

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B-stars
C-stars

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120 35
121 36
122 37

Temperatures
Miscellaneous
Line Areas

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123 38
124 39
125 40
126 42
127 43

Long Dispersion Spectrophotometry
Line Areas
K-Stars
Line Contours; O-stars
 $\mu \phi$ of c-stars

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127.1 52
128 56
129 56
130 57

Identifications (Sequences)
Various Plate Measurements
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(Under C. H. Payne)

Madelen R. Dreyer
Mary L. Miller
Helen M. Lewis

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131	58	Various Plate Measurements	(under C. H. Payne)	Jenka Mohr
132	61	Plm Grating, Cluster Maps, Sequences		
133		Measures by Bond Astr. Club	under C. H. Payne	1928
134		Various Plate Measures		
135		Miscellaneous		1897 Edward C. Pickering
136		Correspondance		E. E. Barnard
137	11	Progress of Draper Catalog		
138		Miscellaneous		
139		Various Plate Measures		1890-95
140	1	Misc. Counts for Annual Report		1899-1900 Edward C. Pickering
141	2	" " " "		1908-18 " "
142	1	Misc. Memoranda		1902-12 " "
143	2	" " " "		1888-95 " "
144		Accident Book		1905-08 " "
145	2	Notebook		
146		Eye Estimates of Stellar Magn. - Instructions		1881 J. Smith
147		Plates + Observations		
148		Measures + Miscellaneous		? Edward C. Pickering
149		Eyepiece Measurements		1877 Frank Wald
150		Financial Record + Other Computations		1906 ? Edward C. Pickering
151		Eclipse Notebook		1888-1900
152	45	Determinations of Parallax by Photog. Means		1882 William H. Pickering
153	44	Preparations for Observing Total Eclipse		1886 " "
154		Various Essays		1878 " "
155		" " " "		1879 " "
156	1	Variables and Asteroids		1914-16 Susan Raymond
157	2	Eros Series Measures, Economic Scale Meas.		1916 " "
158	3	Circumpolar Variables		1916 " "
159	4	Asteroids		1911, 17 " "
160	5	Asteroids, Misc.		1917 " "
161		Misc. Observations (under H H Plashett)		1875-76 William A. Rogers
162		Plates (Nova Aquilae)		1918 Arthur R. Sayer
163		M. determinations		" "
164		Variable Star Observations		1909-10 L. G. Schultz
165		Observations of Nebulae		1900 Delisle Stewart
166		Plate Measures		1923? Rufus O. Suter
167		" " " "		
168		Obs + Calc. - Ecogographical Position		1897? Winslow Upham
169	9	Latitude + Longitude, Arequipa Station		1896? " "

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170	1	Scale Measures - series + Chart Plates	1917-18	Mary H. Vann
171	2	Observations of Novae	1917-18	" "
172	3	" "	1918 -	" "
173	4	" "	1918	" "
174	1	Double Star Measures	1876	Leonard Wald
175		Correspondance	1896-97	Anna Wendell
176		Observations - 6-in Telescope	1911-13	Ida E. Woods
177		SS Cygni	1917	" "
178	1	Instructions, et c.	1915	" "
179		Observations - 6-in Telescope	1913-17	" "
180	4	Cluster Variables	1916	" "
181	5	" "	1917-18	" "
182	6	" "	1919-23	" "
183	7	Examination of AM and AC plates	1919	" "
184	8	Objects suspected as Novae	1919	" "
185	9	Examination of AM and AC plates	1919-20	" "
186	10	Objects looked up for outsiders by request	1921	" "
187	11	New Variables	1921-22	" "
188	12	Examination of AM and AC plates	1920	" "
189	13	Examination of Northern Regions	1920	" "
190	14	Examination of AM and AC plates	1920	" "
191	15	" " " "	1920-21	" "
192	16	Objects suspected as Novae	1921	" "
193	17	Special Objects	1922	" "
194	18	Examination of Southern Regions	1922	" "
195	19	New Variables	1922?	" "
196	20	Special Examination of MC Plates	1922-23	" "
197	21	Nebulae and Asteroids	1923	" "
198	22	Cluster Variables	1923	" "
199	23	" "	1922-23	" "
200	24	Special Examination of MC Plates	1923	" "
201	25	Objects looked up for outsiders	1922	" "
202	26	Special Examination of MC Plates	1921-24	" "
203	27	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1925-28	" "
204	28	" " " "	1924-25	" "
205	29	New Variables	1924-26	" "
206	30	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1924-25	" "
207	31	Cluster Variables	1927	" "
208	32	Misc. Milky Way Regions	1925	" "

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209	33	Objects looked up for outsiders	1922-24 ^{02 04?}	Ida E. Woods
210	34	Milky Way Regions, MC+MF Plates	1926-30	" "
211	35	Interesting Objects, Suspected Variables	1926	" "
212	36	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1926	" "
213	37	" " " "	1926	" "
214	38	" " " "	1926	" "
215	39	New Variables	1926	" "
216	40	Misc. Milky Way Regions	1927-28	" "
217	41	" " " "	1926	" "
218	42	" " " "	1926	" "
219	44	Objects looked up for outsiders	1926	" "
220	45	Cluster Variables	1927	" "
221	46	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1929	" "
222	47	Dr. Gerasimovic, T Pyx, Shapley LPV's	1927	" "
223		Spectrophotometry, Schilt Measures	1931	G. Maulbetsch
224		" " "	1931	"
225		" " "	1932	"
226	140	Variables and Misc.	1905	Oliver C. Wendell
227		A B plates	1934	G. Maulbetsch
228	4	Spectrophotometry	1933	"
229		Computation of Ephemerides	1904-07	? Oliver C. Wendell
230	1	Notes on Orion Cluster, Interstars, B stars		CHL
231		Star Sequences	1926	
232		RB Standard Star Identifications		JME + MM
233	3	Chart Plates	1898-99	Louisa D. Willis
234	1	T Andromedae	1916	H.C. Wilson
235		Doubtful Variable, Misc. Obsn's	1904-12	
236		Pyrheliometer Record	1916	W.
237		" "	1917	
238		Variable Star Observations	1902-03	
239	1	" " "	1903	Marion F. Michaeli
240	1	" " "	1904	G.E.W.
241	"	Meridian Photometer	1907	S.M.P.
242		Halley's Comet Observations	1909	
243		Reduction of Observations for Position	1909-10	Oliver C. Wendell " H.C.
244	3	Nova Aquilae	1918	
245		Comparison Stars	1906-09	
246		Calculations - Schaefer + Others	1905, 1911	
247	1	24-in reflector journal	1907	

See also
"256

052

053

053

054

054

248		Plates, Photometers	1935-36	J. E. Jones
249	94	RH Plates - Photometry	1933	
250		Variable Observations	1907-08	
251		SV Tauri	1925	C. Lanovsky
252	1	Observations	1909	Samuel C. Catterall
253	12	Meridian Photometer	1908	
254	22	Jupiter Eclipses, Variable Stars	1898	
255	23	" " " "	1899	
256	49	New Variable	1926-28	Ilda E. Woods
257	54	Evening Cloud Record	1916-17	
258		Shade Glasses	1902-03	C. H. Olmstead
259	60	Pole Plates (MC) + Misc Experiments		F. Schilt
260	62	Photometric Experiments	1929	
261	63	Variable Star Observations, Photm.	1929	
262	64	" " " "	1929	
263	65	" " " "	1929	
264	66	" " " "	1929	
265	67	" " " "	1929	F. Schilt
266	68	" " " "	1929	"
267	69	" " " "	1929	"
268	71	" " " "	1929	"
269	72	" " " "	1929	"
270	73	" " " "	1929	"
271	74	" " " "	1930	"
272	75	" " " "	1930	"
273	76	RH plates	1930	"
274	77	" "	1930	"
275	78	" "	1930	"
276	79	" "	1930	"
277	80	" "	1930-31	"
278	81	" "	1931	"
279	82	" "	1931	"
280	83	" "	1931	"
281	84	" "	1931-32	"
282	85	" "	1932	"
283	86	" " PTM	1932	"
284	87	" " "	1932	"
285	88	" " "	1932	"
286	89	" " "	1932	"

	287	90	RH Plates	PTM	RB	1932	F. Schilt
	288	91	" "	"	"	1932-33	"
	289	92	" "	"	"	1933-34	"
	290	93	" "	"	"	1933	"
054	291	95	" "	"	"	1933	"
	292	96	" "	"	"	1933-34	"
	293	97	" "	"	"	1934	
	294	98	" "	PTM	RB	1934	
	295	99	" "	"	"	1934	
	296		Equatorial Observations			1877	
	297		Equator Points, Meridian Observations			1877	
	298		Telescope Observations			1878	
055	299	R45	Reduction of Photometric Observations			1878	
	300	R47	"	"	"	1878	
	301	R48	11	Variable Star Observations, Red'm of Phot Obs.		1878	
Dec 11/3/65. 981	302	R50	12	"	"	1878-79	
	303	R51	13	"	"	1879	
	304	R54	15	"	"	1879	
	305	R55	16	"	"	1879	
	306	R91	17	"	"	1879-80	
	307	R92	18	"	"	1880	
	308	R93	19	"	"	1880	
	309	R95	21	"	"	1880-81	
	310	R96	22	"	"	1881	
	311	R98	23	"	"	1881	
	312	R99	24	"	"	1881	Herschel, G. Webb
055	313	R103	29	"	"	1882	
	314	R104	30	"	"	1882-83	
	315	R107		"	"	1883	
	316		38	"	"	1884	
	317			"	"	1885	
	318			"	"	1885-97	
	319			"	"	1885-86	
056	320			"	"	1886-87	
	321a			"	"	1888	
	321b			"	"	1888	
	322a			"	"	1888	
	322b			"	"	1888-89	
	323			"	"	1889	

Various?
Variable Star Observations

324				1889
325	57	"	"	1889-90
326		"	"	1891
327		"	"	1891
328	61	"	"	1891-92
329		"	"	1893
330		"	"	1893
331		"	"	1894
332		"	"	1895
333	78	"	"	1895
334	82	"	"	1895
335	83	"	"	1896
336	84	"	"	1896
337	85	"	"	1896
338	86	"	"	1896
339	87	"	"	1897
340	88	"	"	1897
341	89	"	"	1897
342	90	"	"	1897
343	91	"	"	1897
344	92	"	"	1897
345	93	"	"	1897
346	95	"	"	1898
347	96	"	"	1898
348	97	"	"	1898
349	98	"	"	1898
350	99	"	"	1898
351	100	"	"	1898
352	101	"	"	1898
353	102	"	"	1898
354	103	"	"	1898
355	104	"	"	1899
356	105	"	"	1899
357	106	"	"	1899
358	107	"	"	1899
359	108	"	"	1899
360	109	"	"	1899
361	110	"	"	1899
362	111	"	"	1899

056
See K6-11365
.531-.533

057

See K6-11365
.539

057

058

W. A. Pickering

058
 Continued in
 KG 1136.5.545
 058
 059
 059
 060

363	112	Various? Variable	Star Observations	1899
364	113	"	"	1900
365	114	"	"	1900
366	115	"	"	1900
367	116	"	"	1900
368	117	"	"	1900
369	118	"	"	1900
370	119	"	"	1900
371	120	"	"	1900
372	121	"	"	1900-01
373		Chronograph Record, Zone Stars, 24-in		1877
374	124	Variable Star Observations		1901
375	125	"	"	1901
376	A1	General Catalog, Circle Readings		1871-72
377	A2	"	"	1871-72
378	A3	"	"	1871-73
379	A4	Polar Catalog,	"	1872-73
380	A5	"	"	1872-73
381	A6	"	"	1872-73
382	A7	General Catalog,	"	1874-75
383	A8	"	"	1874-75
384	A9	"	"	1874-75
385	A10	"	"	1874-75
386	A11	"	"	1874-75
387	A12	"	"	1874-75
388	A13	Circle Readings, Fundamental Stars for Zone		1876
389	A14	"	"	1876
390	A15	"	"	1877
391	A16	Maskelyne Fund. Stars, Circle Readings		1877
392	A17	Circle Readings, Zone Fundamental Stars		1877
393	A18	"	"	1878
394	A19	"	"	1878
395	A20	"	"	1879
396	A21	"	"	1879
397	A22	"	"	1879
398	A23	"	"	1879
399	A24	"	"	1879-80
400	A25	"	"	1880
401	A26	"	"	1880

402 A27
 403 A28
 404 A29
 405 A30
 406 A31
 407 A32
 408 A33
 409 A34
 410 A35
 411 A36
 412 A37
 413 A38
 414 A39
 415 A40
 416
 417 A43
 418 B1?
 419
 420 B3
 421 B4
 422 B5
 423 B6
 424 B7
 425 B8
 426 B9
 427 1
 428 2
 429 3
 430 4
 431 5
 432 6
 433 B1
 434 B2
 435 B3
 436 B4
 437 B5
 438 B6
 439 B7
 440

Circle Readings, Fundamental Stars 1880
 " " " " 1880
 " " " " 1880-81
 " " " " 1881
 " " " " 1881
 Fundamental Stars, Observations 1881
 " " " " 1881-83
 Circle Readings, Fundamental Stars 1883
 " " " " 1883
 " " " " 1883
 " " " " 1883
 " " " " 1883-84
 " " " " 1884
 " " " " Fund + Zone Stars 1884-85
 " " " " " 1885
 " " " " " 1885-86
 " " " " " 1877
 Observation for Inclination of Declination Wire 1878-79
 Polaris Circle Readings + Observations 1879
 " " " " " 1879-80
 " " " " " 1880
 " " " " " 1880-81
 " " " " " 1881-82
 " " " " " 1883-84
 " " " " " 1884
 Zone measurements 1882
 Revision of Equatorial Zone 1883
 " " " " " 1883
 " " " " " 1883
 " " " " " 1883
 " " " " " 1883
 Fundamental Stars for Zones 1870-71
 " " " " " 1871
 " " " " " 1871
 " " " " " 1871
 " " " " " 1872
 " " " " " 1872
 " " " " " 1872
 " " " " (Obsura + Reduction) 1870-71

WSR + AM
 (Augustus
 McCannell
 ?)

060

060

061

061

061

441 F11

Fundamental Stars, Observations + Reductions

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442 F12

" " " "

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443 F13

" " " "

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444 F14

General Catalog

" "

1871-72

445 F15

" "

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1871

446 F16

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1871-72

062

447 F17

" "

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1871

448 F18

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1871-72

449 F19

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1871-72

450 F20

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1871-72

451 F21

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1871-72

452 F22

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1872

453 F23

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1872

454 F24

" "

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455 F26

Polar Catalog

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1872-73

456 F27

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1872-73

457 F28

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1872-73

458 F29

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1872-73

459 F30

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1872-73

460 F31

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1872-73

461 F32

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1872-73

462 F33

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1872-73

463 F34

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1872-73

464 F35

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1872-73

062

465 F36

" "

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1872-73

466 F37

" "

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1874-75

467 F38

" "

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468 F39

General Catalogue

" "

1874-75

469 F40

" "

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470 F41

" "

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1874-75

471 F42

" "

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1874-75

063

472 F43

" "

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1874-75

473 F44

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1874-75

474 F45

" "

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1874-75

475 F46

" "

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1874-75

476 F47

" "

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1874-75

477 F48

Fundamental Stars

" "

1876-77

478 F49

" "

" "

1876-77

479 F50

" "

" "

1876-77

	480	F51	Fundamental Stars, Observation + Reduction	1876-77
	481	F52	" " " "	1876-77
	482	F53	" " " "	1876-77
	483	F54	" " " "	1877
	484	F55	" " (+2ms) "	1877
	485	F56	Maskelyne Fundamentals	1877
	486	-	Meridian Circle	1875
	487	F57	Maskelyne Fundamentals	1877
	488	F59	Fundamental stars	1878
	489	F60	" "	1878
	490	F61	" "	1878
	491	F62	" "	1878
	492	F63	Coast Survey Catalog	1878
	493	F64	" " "	1878
	494	F65	" " "	1878
	495	F66	Miscellaneous stars	1878
	496	F67	Fundamental Stars, Observation + Reduction	1879
	497	F68	" " " "	1879
	498	F69	" " " "	1879
	499	F70	" " " "	1879
	500	F71	" " " "	1879
	501	F72	" " " "	1879
	502	F73	" " " "	1879
	503	F74	" " " "	1879
	504	F75	" " " "	1880
	505	F76	" " " "	1880
	506	F77	" " " "	1880
	507	F78	" " " "	1880
	508	F79	" " " "	1880
	509	F80	" " " "	1880
	510	F81	" " " "	1880
	511	F82	" " " "	1880
	512	F83	" " " "	1881
	513	F84	" " " "	1881
	514	F85	" " " "	1881
	515	F90	" " " "	-
	516	F89	" " " "	-
	517	F88	" " " "	1881
	518	F87	" " " "	1882

063

063

064

064

065

065

519	F86	Fundamental Stars, Observations + Reductions	1882
520	E1	Flexure, Collimation Runs	1879
521	E2	" " "	1879-80
522	E4	" " "	1880-81
523	E5	" " "	1881
524	E6	" " "	1881-83
525	E7	" " "	1883
526	E8	" " "	1883-84
527	E9	" " "	1884
528	E10	" " "	1885-86

Zone Chronograph Records

529	A1	Zone Chronograph Records	1870
530	A2	" " "	1870
531	A3	" " "	1871
532	A4	" " "	1871
533	A5	" " "	1871
534	A6	" " "	1871

Zone Circle Readings

Zone Chronograph Records

535	C6'	Zone Circle Readings	1871
536	A7	Zone Chronograph Records	1871
537	A8	" " "	1871-72
538	A9	" " "	1872
539	A10	" " "	1872-73
540	A11	" " "	1873
541	A12	" " "	1873-74
542	A13	" " "	1874
543	A14	" " "	1874
544	A15	" " "	1874
545	A16	" " "	1874-75
546	A17	" " "	1875
547	A18	" " "	1875
548	A19	" " "	1875
549	A20	" " "	1875-76
550	A21	" " "	1876
551	A22	" " "	1876-77
552	A26	" " "	1878-79
553	A25	" " "	1877-78
554	A23	" " "	1877

066

Polaris, Observations + Reductions

555	B1	Polaris, Observations + Reductions	1879
556	B2	" " "	1879-80
557	B3	" " "	1880

66

066

558 B4
 559 B5
 560 B6
 561 B2
 562 B3

Polaris, Observations + Reductions

1880-81

" " "
 " " "
 " " "
 " " "

1881
 1881-83
 1883
 1883-84

Zone Observations + Reductions

1870

563 C1
 564 C2
 565 C3
 566 C4
 567 C5

" " "
 " " "
 " " "
 " " "

1870-71
 1871
 1871
 1871

066

568 C6
 569 C7
 570 C8

" " "
 " " "
 " " "

1871
 1871
 1871

067

571 C9
 572 C10
 573 C11

" " "
 " " "
 " " "

1871
 1871
 1871

missing?

574 C12
 575 C13
 576 C14

" " "
 " " "
 " " "

1871
 1871-72
 1872

577 C15
 578 C16
 579 C17

" " "
 " " "
 " " "

1872-73
 1873
 1873

067

580 C18
 581 C19
 582 C20

" " "
 " " "
 " " "

1873-74
 1873
 1874

583 C21
 584 C22
 585 C23

" " "
 " " "
 " " "

1874
 1874
 1874

586 C24
 587 C25
 588 C26

" " "
 " " "
 " " "

1874
 1874
 1874

589 C27
 590 C28
 591 C29

" " "
 " " "
 " " "

1874-75
 1875
 1875

592 C30
 593 C31
 594 C32

" " "
 " " "
 " " "

1875
 1875
 1875

67

595 C33
 596 C34

" " "
 " " "

1875-76
 1876

J1
J2

or 11366.
871 and
872

069

missing 11/1991
missing 11/1991

069

070

070

636	J3
637	J4
638	J5
639	J6
640	J7
641	J8
642	J9
643	J10
644	J11
645	J12
646	J13
647	J14
648	J15
649	J16
650	J17
651	J18
652	J19
653	J21
654	J22
655	J24
656	J25
657	J26
658	J27
659	J28
660	J29
661	J30
662	
663	
664	
665	
666	
667	T6
668	
669	T9
670	
671	
672	
673	
674	K1

Chronograph Record

1871	A. McConnell
1871	"
1872	W. A. Rogers
1872	"
1872-73	"
1873	"
1873-74	"
1874	"
1874-75	"
1875	"
1875-76	"
1876	"
1876	"
1876-77	"
1877	"
1877	"
1878-79	"
1879-80	"
1880	"
1880-81	W. V. Brown
1881	"
1881	"
1881-82	"
1883	"
1883	"
1883-84	"

Reports, Meteorological Notes

1889-94	
1886-88	
1883-85	
1897-1901	
1896-1902	
1895, 97, 1901	
1903	
1896?	
1896	
1899	
1902	
1871-72	W. A. Rogers A. McConnell

North Pole Reductions
 South Pole Reductions
 Variable Stars, Computations
 Tabulations of Observations of Variable Stars
 Memoranda and Reminders
 Bright Double Stars, Working Lists
 Current Relative + Absolute Estimates, Variable Stars
 Variable Stars, Computations
 Ephemerides of Variable Stars
 Clock Errors, Instrumental Constants

070

071

071

072

675 K2
 676 K3
 677 K4
 678 K5
 679 K6
 680 K7
 681 K9
 682 K10
 683 K12
 684 K13
 685 K14
 686 K15
 687 K16
 688 K17
 689 K18
 690 K19
 691 K20
 692 K21
 693 K22
 694 K23
 695 K26
 696 K27
 697 K28
 698 J1
 699 J2
 700 J3
 701 J4
 702 J5
 703 J6
 704
 705
 706 D4
 707 D8
 708 D9
 709 D10
 710 R14
 711 R17
 712 R18
 713 R27

Clock Errors, Polar Catalog, Instrumental Constants 1872-73
 " " General " " " 1874-75
 " " " " " 1878-79
 " " " " " 1883
 Equator Points, Corrections 1871-73
 " " " " Flexure, Polar Cat. 1872-73
 " " " " Constants 1878
 Equator Pt. from Observ of α + δ U Mi 1876
 Copy of Instrumental Constants 1870-71; Redetermin. of $\Delta T, m, h'$ 1870-78
 Instrumental Constants depending on Pulkovo Coordinates 1871-72
 " " " " " 1872-73
 " " " " " 1873-74
 " " " " " 1875
 " " " " " 1876
 " " " " " 1877
 " " " " " 1877
 Final Values of $\Delta T, m + \text{Req}$ for Reduction of Zone Obsns 1870-74
 " " " " " " " 1874-78
 " " " and c 1872-76
 " " " " " 1870-72 1876-78
 Meridian Circle Constants, A, Star Constants 1872
 Instrumental Constants, Star Constants 1876
 Inclination of Declination Wires 1877
 DM places for 1855 + 1875; Zone Obsns, Final Red'ns
 " " " " " " " " " " "
 " " " " " " " " " " "
 " " " " " " " " " " "
 " " " " " " " " " " "
 " " " " " " " " " " "
 " " " " " " " " " " "
 DM list +53° +54° 1883
 " " +50°, +51°, +52°
 Thermometer, Barometer Runs 1873
 " " " " " 1875
 " " " " " 1875-76
 " " " " " 1876
 Planet + Satellite Observations
 Star Observations 1877-78
 " " " " " 1877-78
 " " " " " 1869 + before

W.A. Rogers + JFM

W.A. Rogers

JFV

Supplement list

072

072

073

073

714	R67		Meteorological Record	1880-82	
715		10	Notes on S.M.P.	1892	
716		12	Micrometer Level	1877	
717		17	Reduction of Observations by Schmidt by Reed		
718		33	Early lists of Gaseous Neb, Stars Rec. Spectra	1880	
719		34	Discussion of H.A. 24, Group M.P. accord to DM		
720		35	" " " " " " " " " " " "		
721		38	Stars + Clusters, Lists with X Plates Entered	1899	
722			Double Stars		
723			" " " " " " " " " " " "		
724			Asteroid Zone Book		
725		#3	Eros Book	1893	
726		#4	" " " " " " " " " " " "	1876	
727			Zone Stars	1870	
728	U4		Russian Transit		
729	U5		Zone Circle ^{Recordings} Readings	1870	
730	U6		" " " " " " " " " " " "		
731	U7		" " " " " " " " " " " "	1871	
732	U10		D.M. List		
733	U		Brown's Note Book	1880	
734	U		Record of work by D.B. Pratt	1883-84	D.B. Pratt
735	U14		Stars (Zone) Needing Re-examination of chronograph sheets	1871	
736	U15		Stars to be re-observed		
737	U16		Star places	1875.0	
738	U17	1	K'K d d'		
739	U18	3	" " " " " " " " " " " "		
740	U19		Zero stars, Red. to apparent place		
741	U20		Table for Reductions		
742	U22		Fundamental Stars, Ephemerides	1879	
743	U23		" " " " " " " " " " " "	1879	
744	U24		Working Lists, Fundamental Stars	1879	
745	U25		" " " " " " " " " " " "	1879	
746	U27		Longitude Campaign - Obs. + Red.	1872-73	
747	U28		Miscellaneous Observations	1881	
748	U30		Montreal - Cambridge Longitude Observations	1883	
749	U31		Longitude Campaign: Montreal - Cambridge	1883	
750	U34		General Catalog List		
751	U37		? (Bork)	1875	W.A. Rogers
752			Missing		

073

074

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753 U40
 754 U41
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753	U40	Chronograph Record		
754	U41	List of Polar stars w/ dates of Obs	1885	
755		Flexure Collimation Revers	1880	W.C.
756		Investigation of Circle Observations	1879	
757		Longitude of Circle Errors	1881	
758		Investigation of Circle - Discussion		
759		" of Errors of West Circle from Stops	1884	
760		" of Circle	1877-79	
761		" " Observations	1871-79	
762		Investigation of Errors of West Circle for Stops	1884-85	
763		" " " " "	1885	
764		" " " " "	1885	
765		" " " " "	1885	
766		Investigation of Circle Observations	1879	
767	# 3	Jupiter Ecl. + Var. Stars	1900	
768	# 4	" " " "	1902	
769	# 6	" " " "	1894	
770	# 9	" " " "	1903	RWH
771		Various Stars Zone P.M. XI		
772		" " " " XII		
773		Arequipa Time Book No. 1	1891-92	J.A. Dunne v LW
774		Chronograph Comparisons	1892	
775		Comparison of Waltham Clock w/ Smith Clock	1878	W.A. Rogers WH + J.A. Dunne
776		Error of sidereal Clock	1908	
777		" " "	1913	Philip O'Reilly
778		" " "	1911	" "
779		" " "	1910	" "
780		Observations	1876	W.A. Rogers
781		Time Book	1875	" "
782		" "	1874	" "
783		" "	1874	" "
784		" "	1874	" "
785		Time Service [Clock Errors?]	1879	" "
786		Clock Errors	1878	" "
787		Time Service	1888-90	
788		" "	1890-91	J.A. Dunne
789		" "	1891	" "
790		" " + Russian Transit	1877	L. Waldo
791		Check Readings of Sheets of Obs. for Longitude	1871	H. Gannett

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075 794
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075 802
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MISSING 4/1971 807
076 808
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076 821
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Russian Transit	1883	
Time Service, Clock Errors + Russian Transit	1877	L. Waldo
" " " " " "	1877	"
" " Clock Comparisons	1881	F. Waldo
Level of East Transit	1877	L. Waldo
Time Service	1887-88	
" "	1882-83	
" "	1892-94	J.A. Dunne
" "	1880	Harriet Wace
" " Clock Comparisons	1879-80	F. Waldo
" " " "	1878-79	L. Waldo
Reference Book: Stars, Asteroids, etc. under observation		
Errata in Rogers' AGC Catalogue	1904	J.A. Dunne
Meridian Circle - General Record	1879-80	W.A. Rogers
Constellations		
Working List of Star Data	1871	
" " " " for 1880	1880-81	
Constellation Data	1879-80	
Reduction of Bonn Observations from 1855 to 1875		
Discordant stars		
Reports on Obsn of Stars in N. Hemisphere to 9 th mag, Pulkovo	1879	
Star Reduction	1890	
Measures of Plates	1890	
No. 2 Computations - long & short of Bohrian + Peruvia Station	1894	
Zone Observations	1883-84	
No. 1 Measurements: WA Rogers Micrometer	1894-97	
Sun Images	1880	D.C. Bard
Miscellaneous Notes		Bard
Chronograph Sheet Readings	1884	
Computation of Residuals		
Corrections for Error	1869-70	
Observations of Southern Variable Stars	1899-1904	
Nautical Almanac	1883	
Lunar Brightness	1881	
XII 12-in Horizontal Telescope records	1899	
Satellite IV	1888-90	
Reductions		
Bibliography		
Observations & Reductions Part II	1876	

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	831	Observations + Reductions, Part III	1876	
	832	Re-readings of Chronograph sheets	1880	
077	833	Investigations of Division Errors of Circle "East"	1880-81	
	834	Chronograph Readings	1881	H. Stevens
	835	Readings of Chronograph sheets	1879	L. Waldo
	836	Star Data	1884-85	
	837	" "	1882	
	838	Star + Comet Data	1881-84	P.C. Ricketts
	839	Reductions	1880-81	S.C. Chandler
	840	Comet Data + Companion Stars	1881	
	841	Time Service	1885-86	W.A. Rogers
077	842	Dates of Observations of Zone Stars for 1883+1884		
	843	Miscellaneous Star Observations		
	844	Star Observations		
	845	Zone Observations	1884	
	846	Fundamental Zone stars - Circle Readings	1885	
	847	J 2 Current Observations of Variable Stars	1895-96	
	848	Record of Observations	1898-99	F.W. Grover
	849	Variable Star Observations	1899-1900	H.C. Bailey
	850	Absolute Work Runs 1879, 80, 81	1898-99	
078	851	(Variable Stars)	1883-84	
	852	West Dome 6 1/4"	1883	S.C. Chandler
	853	" " "	1883	
	854	" " "	1896-98	
	855	Wedge Zones	1887-	
	856	Correction to Ephemeris - Jupiter's Satellites		
	857	Final Adopted Maps: Comp. Stars for Variables	c 1901	
	858	" " " " " "	c 1900	
	859	Variables + Other Stars - Naked Eye Obsns.	1889-1890	
	860	Variable Star Observations	1894-95	H.C. Bailey
	861	19 Variable Stars	1898-99	
078	862	18 Computation Book	1899-1900	
	863	17 " "	c 1902	
	864	Wedge Photometer Zone Stars	1894-	
	865	Meridian Photometry	1881-84	
	866	Multiple Theory (H.N. Russell) - Notes	1925	
	867	Plates to be Examined re Peters' Zones	1877-78	
	868	R21 Equatorial Zones	1877	
079	869	Location of Comparison Stars for Variable	1894	

Harvard Lunar Plates

Mary Fowler

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909	<u>XXXIII</u>	"	"	"	1599	1606	
910	<u>XXXIV</u>	"	"	"	1607	1662	1668
911	<u>XXXV</u>	"	"	"	1669	1674	1675
912	<u>XXXVI</u>	"	"	"	1682	1683	1696
913	<u>XXXVII</u>	"	"	"	1697	1702	1703
914	<u>XXXVIII</u>	"	"	"	1737	1739	1743
915	<u>XXXIX</u>	"	"	"	1744	1747	
916	<u>XL</u>	"	"	"	1749	1750	1751
917	<u>XL I</u>	"	"	"	1759	1760	1790
918	<u>XL II</u>	"	"	"	1791	1795	
919	<u>XL III</u>	"	"	"	1796	1801	1802
920	<u>XL IV</u>	"	"	"	1808	1809	1826
921	<u>XL V</u>	"	"	"	1827	1884	
922	<u>XL VI</u>	"	"	"	1885	1889	1890
923	<u>XL VII</u>	"	"	"	1930	1931	1956
924	<u>XL VIII</u>	"	"	"	1957	1963	1964
925	<u>XL IX</u>	"	"	"	1973	1974	
926	<u>L</u>	"	"	"	1980	1981	2009
927	<u>LI</u>	"	"	"	2010	2011	2012
928	<u>L II</u>	"	"	"	2014	2015	2074
929	<u>L III</u>	"	"	"	2076	2081	2082
930	<u>L IV</u>	"	"	"	2093	2094	2145
931	<u>L V</u>	"	"	"	2146	2172	
932	<u>L VI</u>	"	"	"	2173	2180	2181
933	<u>L VII</u>	"	"	"	2184	2185	2234
934	<u>L VIII</u>	"	"	"	2235	2367	2368
935	<u>L IX</u>	"	"	"	2374	2375	2377
936	<u>L X</u>	"	"	"	2378	2386	2387
937	<u>L XI</u>	"	"	"	2493	2494	2782
938	<u>L XII</u>	"	"	"	2783	2797	2798
939	<u>L XIII</u>	"	"	"	2371	2182	2368 (Remasures)
940	<u>L XIV</u>	"	"	"	2992	2994	3008
941	<u>L XV</u>	"	"	"	3010	3023	3024
942	<u>L XV</u> [sic]	"	"	"	1698	1748	
943	<u>L XVI</u>	"	"	"	2751	2752	
944	<u>L XVII</u>	"	"	"	3045	3046	3189
945	<u>L XVIII</u>	"	"	"	3215	3376	
946	<u>L XIX</u>	"	"	"	3377	3385	3384
947	<u>L XX</u>	"	"	"	3485	3486	3535

Harvard Lunar Plates

081

081

Note gaps

081

082

948	LXXI			3536	3601	
949	LXXII	"	"	3648	3649	
950	LXXIII	"	"	3669	3783	
951	LXXIV	"	"	3784	3811	
952	LXXV	"	"	3812	3844	
953	LXXVI	"	"	3846	3856	
954	LXXVII	"	"	3857	4096	
955	LXXVIII	"	"	4097	4239	
956	LXXIX	"	"	4271	4272	
957	LXXX	"	"	4295	4296	
958	LXXXI	"	"	4297	4298	
959	LXXXII	"	"	4303	4304	4309
960	LXXXIII	"	"	4336	4374	4375
961	LXXXIV	"	"	4423	4424	4455
962	LXXXV	"	"	4456	4465	4466
963	LXXXVI	"	"	4478	4481	
964	LXXXVII	"	"	4503	4554	4555
965	LXXXVIII	"	"	4571	4572	4588
966	LXXXIX	"	"	4589	4619	4620
967	XC	"	"	4677	4678	4690
> 968	CXV	"	"	7549	7571	7572
969	CXVI	"	"	7665	7666	7677
970	CXVII	"	"	7678	7692	7693
971	CXVIII	"	"	7965	7966	7990
972	CXIX	"	"	8013	8014	8052
973	CXX	"	"	8110	8288	8289
974	CXXI	"	"	8299	8300	8306
975	CXXII	"	"	8307	8316	8317
976	CXXIII	"	"	8346	8347	8362
977	CXXIV	"	"	8635	8636	8639
978	CXXV	"	"	8640	8904	8905
979	CXXVI	"	"	8649	8650	8690
→ 980	CXXVII	"	"	8728	8729	
981	CXXVIII	"	"	8726	8727	8731
982	CXXIX	"	"	8732	8890	8891
983	CXXX	"	"	9079	9080	9086
984	CXXXI	"	"	9087	9193	9194
985	CXXXII	"	"	9195	9249	9250
986	CXXXIII	"	"	9263	9264	9286

Mary Fowler

Martha C. Borch

Mary Fowler

Martha C Borch

82
See 1068
for missing
volumes

Harvard Lunar Plates

- 987 CXXXIV
- 988 CXXXV
- 989 CXXXVII
- 990 CXXXVIII
- 991 CXXXIX
- 992 CXL
- 993 CXLI
- 994 CXLI
- 995 CXLIII
- 996 CXLIV
- 997 CXLV
- 998 CXLVI
- 999 CXLVII
- 1000 CXLVIII
- 1001 CXLIX
- 1002 CL
- 1003 CLI
- 1004 CLII
- 1005 CLIII
- 1006 CLIV
- 1007 CLV
- 1008 CLVI
- 1009 CLVII
- 1010 CLVIII
- 1011 CLIX
- 1012 CLX
- 1013 CLXI
- 1014 CLXII
- 1015 CLXIII
- 1016 CLXIV
- 1017 CLXV
- 1018 CLXVI
- 1019 CLXVII
- 1020 CLXVIII
- 1021 CLXIX
- 1022 CLXX
- 1023 CLXXI
- 1024 CLXXII
- 1025 CLXXIII

082

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- 9377 9378 9388
- 9389 9413 9414
- 9461 9492 9491
- 9495 9496 9732
- 9733 9754 9782
- 9783 9785 9786
- 9817 9818 9859
- 9860 9997 9998
- 10030 10031 10072
- 10073 10103 [10102]
- 10227 10228 10231
- 10232 10263 10264
- 10385 10386 10532
- 10533 10609 10760
- 10692 10693 10701
- 10702 10716 10718
- 10737 10738 10743
- 10746 10748 10753
- 10761 10933 10934
- 10605 10998 10999
- 11004 11006 11039
- 11160 [11161] 11197
- 11198 11201 11202
- 11208 11209 11218
- 11219 11276 11285
- 11286 11301 11302
- 11314 11315 11522
- 11331 11336 11337
- 11523 11542 11544
- 11549 11550 11580
- 11581 11597 11598
- 11636 11705 11709
- 11870 11871 11890
- 11891 11909 11910
- 11924 11925 11931
- 11932 11997 11998
- 12017 12018 12027
- 12028 12043 12044
- 12065 12069 12075

- Martha C. Borton
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- Ernestine Fuller
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083

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missing
vol 1

1026	CLXXIV	Harvard Lunar Plates	12076	12266	12267	Martha C. Bortin
1027	CLXXV	" " "	12280	12281	12296	" "
1028	CLXXVI	" " "	12301	12300	12297	Ernestine Fuller?
1029	CLXXVII	" " "	12323	12324	12469	" "
1030	CLXXVIII	" " "	12470	12474	12475	" "
1031	CLXXIX	" " "	12507	12508	12525	" "
1032	CLXXX	" " "	12526	12723	12724	" "
1033	CLXXXI	" " "	12740	12791	12774	" "
1034	CLXXXII	" " "	12775	13018	13019	" "
1035	CLXXXIV	" " "	13085	13274	13273	" "
1036	CLXXXV	" " "	13109	13110	13124	Martha C. Bortin
1037	CLXXXVI	" " "	13125	13143	13145	" "
1038	CLXXXVII	" " "	13284	13285	13307	Ernestine Fuller?
1039	CLXXXVIII	" " "	13308	13329	13330	" "
1040	CLXXXIX	" " "	13609	13611	13626	Martha C. Bortin
1041	CXC	" " "	13627	13641	13642	" "
1042	CXC I	" " "	13668	13669	13716	Ernestine Fuller?
1043	CXC II	" " "	13610	13645	13646	Martha C. Bortin
1044	(193)	" " "	13717	13935	13936	Ernestine Fuller?
1045	(194)	" " "	13621	13622	13140	Martha C. Bortin
1046	(195)	" " "	13142			" "
1047	(196)	" " "	13331	13332	13305	Ernestine Fuller?
1048		" " Plate characteristics	12017	- 144	55	
1049		Neptune Plates (Princeton?)	7099	7534		
1050		Neptune "				
1051		Measures of Halannde 20406				Fowler
1052		?	4296	4295		"
1053		Neptune Plates				H. N. Russell
1054		Harvard Lunar Plates				H. N. Russell
1055		Supplementary Notes + Data				
1056		Hayn's Correction for plates of Oct 7, 1911				
1057		Harvard Lunar Plates	13306	12319	12320	Ernestine Fuller?
1058		Neptune Plates				Fowler
1059		Supplementary Notes	3535	- 11998		
1060		Harvard Lunar plates	14455			Ernestine Fuller
1061		" " "	14448	14449	14454	" "
1062		" " "	14408	14416	14417	" "
1063		" " "	14399	14400	14407	" "
1064		" " "	14095	14131	14132	" "

	1065		Harvard Lunar Plates	14045	14046	14094	Ernestine Fuller
083	1066			13959	14027	14028	" "
	1067			13914	13915	13958	" "
(Belonging to)	1068	CXXXVI		9421	9422	9460	" "
084	1069	Fisher	Fireballs - General; Index				PAMPHLET CASE
085	1070	"	Correspondance (Lunar Eclipse)				" "
086	1071	"	Bright Meteors Reported to HCO 1925-32				" "
087	1072	"	Fireballs, Lunar Eclipse				" "
088	1073	"	Meteors + Fireballs				" "
089	1074	"	Meteors (includes painting)				" "
090	1075	"	Meteors, Lunar Eclipse				" "
091	1076	"	Meteors, Fireballs				" "
092	1077	"	Meteors				" "
093	1078	"	Meteors				" "
094	1079	"	Meteors (Newspaper clippings)				" "
095	1080		Observations ~ 1881 ff. - Pickering + Chandler				" "
096	1081	Fisher	Meteor Reports, etc.				" "

DATA NOTEBOOKS, boxes 262-272

No.

box 262

box 263

000	—		Visual Obs'ns (Peru)	8/1894 - 7/1896	S. I. Bailey
001	1		Variable stars in W Cen	11/1898 - 12/1898	"
002	2		" " W Cen, M5	2/1899 - 8/1901	"
003	3		" " M3	6/1900 - 9/1901	"
004	4		" " M3, M5	12/1901 - 9/1912	"
005	—		" " NGC 7078, 6656, M22	7/1907 - 10/1920	" + Gould
006	—		Msc. Var. + " " NGC 7078, 6656, M3, M5	1/1902; 4/1910 - 12/1915	"
007	—		Var. Stars in many clusters	5/1922 - 2/1923	"
008	G1		Star counts, Neb. on Map of Sky, LMC, Glob.	3/1906 - 1/1907	"
009	G2		Nebulae	1/1907 - 9/1908	"
010	G3		Nebulae	9/1908 - 10/1911	"
011	G4	V. I	Positions of Nebulae	4/1908 - 7/1908	?
012	G5	V. III	" " "	9/1908 - 10/1908	?
013	G6	V. IV	" " "	10/1908 - 12/1908	?
014	G7	V. V	" " "	12/1908 - 3/1909	?
015	G8	V. VI	" " "	3/1909 - 4/1909	?
016	G9	V. VII	" " "	4/1909 - 8/1909	?
017	G10	V. VIII	" " "	6/1909 - 9/1909	?
018	G11	V. IX	" " "	9/1909 - 10/1909	?
019	G12	V. X	" " "	11/1909 - 8/1910	?
020	G13	V. XI	" " "	8/1910 - 9/1910	?
021	G14	1	" " " marked by Dr Shalley	? - 7/1923	?
022	G15	2	" " " " " "	7/1923 - 8/1923	Leon Campbell, Jr.
023	G16	1	" " " disc. by D. Menzel	7/1922 - 8/1922	D. Menzel
024	G17	2	" " " " " "	8/1922	"
025	G18	3	" " " " " "	8/1922	"
026	G19	4	" " " " " "	8/1922	"
027	G20	1	" " " Coma-Virgo	2/1927 - 3/1927	A. Ames
028	G21	2	" " " " " "	1927?	"
029	G22	3	" " " " " "	1927?	"
030	G23	4	" " " " " "	?	"
031	G24	5	" " " " " "	?	"
032	G25	6	Diagn. Conc. Form " " "	"	"
033	G26	7	Positions, Magn, dia " " "	"	"
034	G27	8	" " " " " "	"	"
035	G28	9	" " " S. gal. Pole	"	"
036	G29	10	" " " C.-V. ext. -30° to -60°	"	"
037	G30	11	Ident + Mag. NGC Objects	"	"
038	G31	12	" " " Coma-Vir ext.	"	"

box
264

039	G32	13
040	G33	1
041	G34	2
042	G35	3
043	G36	4
044	G37	5
045	G38	6
046	G39	7
047	G40	8
048	G41	9
049	G42	10
050	G43	11
051	G44	12
052	G45	13
053	G46	14
054	G47	A

box
265

055	G48	B
056	G49	C
057	G50	D
058	G51	E
059	G52	F
060	G53	G
061	G54	H
062	G55	J
063	G56	K
064	G57	L
065	G58	M
066	G59	N
067	G60	O
068	G61	P
069	G62	Q
070	G63	R
071	G64	S
072	G65	T
073	G66	U
074	G67	V
075	G68	W
076	G69	X
077	G70	Y

Plate covers Coma-Vir ant ?

Positions of new neb on A plates ?

Positions of nebulae ?

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" " M.E. + S.F. Musser

" " " "

" " " "

" " ? ?

summary of work accomplished

Class + Diagrams

Magnitudes of Nebulae

Class + Diagrams.

Class + Diagrams

Nebula Counts per Sq. Degree

Magnitudes of Clusters of Nebulae

Magnitudes of Nebulae

Diagrams of Brightest Nebulae

Magnitudes of Nebulae

" " "

" " "

" " "

Classifications

Magnitudes

Classification + Diagrams

Magnitudes

" " "

Classifications

Magnitudes

" " "

" " "

" " "

+R.W.F. A. Ame

C.D. Boyd

S.F. Musser

M.E. Musser

S.F. Musser

"

M.E. Musser

"

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M.E. + S.F. Musser

" "

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S.F. Musser

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"

M.E. Musser

M.E. + S.F. Musser

S.F. Musser

M.E. Musser

"

S.F. Musser

M.E. Musser

S.F. Musser

"

M.E. Musser

"

M.E. M. S.

M.M. Seyfert

"

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box
266

box
267

078	G71	Z	Magnitudes of Nebulae		MM Seyfert
079	G72	A'	Examination of A plates	1936-39	various
080	G73	B'	Magnitudes of Nebulae		M.M. Seyfert
081	G74	C'	" "		"
082	G75	D'	" "		MMS + CDB
083	G76	F'	Revised Nebulae Counts		?
084	G77	G'	Magnitudes of Nebulae		CDB, FWU
085	G78	H'	" "		" "
086	G79	I'	" "		" "
087	G80	J'	Positions		? ?
088	G81	K'	Magnitudes		CDB, FWU
089	G82	L'	" "		" "
090	G83	M'	" "		" "
091	G84	N'	" "		CDB
092	G85	O'	" "		CDB, FWU
093	G86	P'	" "		" "
094	G87	Q'	" "		" "
095	G88	R'	" "		" "
096	G89	S'	" "		" "
097	G90	T'	" "		" "
098	G91	U'	" "		" "
099	G92	V'	" "		" "
100	G93	W'	" "		" "
101	G94	X'	" "		" "
102	G95	Y'	" "		" "
103	G96	Z'	" "		FWU
104	G97		Examination		"
105	G101	Vol I	Coma-Virgo Ext. Magnitudes	1935	J. Cuffey
106	G102	Vol II	" " " "	1935	"
107	G103		Nebular Counts	1935-37	Mrs. Lindsay
108	G104		Positions of Nebulae		
109	G105		Magnitudes of Faint Nebulae		
110	G106		Magnitudes of Nebulae	1938-39	C.D. Boyd
111	G107		N.G. Cap Magnitudes		J. Mohr
112	G108		Magnitudes of Nebulae		C.D. Boyd
113	G109		" "		"
114	G110		" "		"
115	G111		" "		"
116	G112		" "		"

box
268

117 G113
 118 G114
 119 G115
 120 G116
 121 G117 M1
 122 G118 M2
 123 G119
 124 G125
 125 G126
 126 G127 1
 127 G128
 128 G129
 129 G130
 130 G131
 131 G132
 132 G133
 133 G134
 134 G135
 135 G136
 136 G137
 137 G138 MCVII
 138 G139 MCVIII
 139 G140 MCIX
 140 G141 MCX
 141 G142 MCXI
 142 G143 MCXII
 143 G144 MCXIII
 144 G145 MCXIV
 145 G146 MCXV

Magnitudes of Nebulae
 Magnitudes, Diameters of Nebulae
 Magnitudes of Nebulae
 Mags. on Overlapping Plates
 15th Mag. Survey
 " " "
 " " "
 " " "
 1935
 Classification + Diameter
 " "
 Positions
 Magnitudes
 Magnitudes
 MC Records of Nebulae; Summary
 MC Magnitude of Nebulae
 MC Classification + Diameters
 MC Nebula Count
 MC North Polar Cap: Positions
 MC Plate Centers
 MC North Polar Cap: Magnitudes
 " " " "
 MC Magnitudes
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C.D. B...
 R.L. Paraboloschi
 F.W. Wright
 "
 J. Mohr
 "
 N.J. Oliver
 C.K. Seyfert
 "
 "
 "
 "
 M.E.M
 P.B.J

Box
269

146 1
 147 2
 148 3
 149 4
 150 5
 151 6a
 152 6b
 153 8
 154 9
 155 10

Variables in SMC, LMC
 " " "
 " "
 " Vela-Carina
 " SMC
 " "
 " LMC, SMC
 " "
 " SMC
 "

1935-39
 RK Marshall
 FW W, VMcK
 RA Craig
 VMcK, N.
 A.F. Swain
 VMcK N
 FW W
 1945
 A.S. Carlston
 FW W, V...
 1941, 51
 S&B, FW W
 A. Hearn
 M.D. Ashbush
 FW W, VMcK
 RK Marshall
 E.M. Coote
 VMcK Nail

	156	11	Variables in SMC, 30 Dor		M. R. Hunt V. McK.
	157	12	" " " 47 Tuc		V. McK.
	158	13	" " LMC, SMC.		M. S. Matthews V. McK. & N.
	159	14	" " " "		FWW et al.
	160	15	" SMC, 47 Tuc, NGC 362		V. McK. & N. ?
	161	16	" SMC, LMC		
Box 269	162	18	" SMC	1932	M. B. Leavens M. B. Shallop V. McK. & N.
	163	19	MWF 182, MWF 188, SMC, LMC		
	164	28	M 55, LMC variables	1934	J. Mohr + V. McK.
	165	30	Variables in LMC	1954-55	V. McK. & N.
	166	31	" "	1952	B. Lindqvist V. McK. & N.
	167	32	" "		M. Ryder
	168	33	" "		
	169	34	" LMC, SMC	1950 1953-54	M. L. Miller J. Swartzman W. Tiffet H. S. Leavitt S. F. Finsen
	170	35	Variables in LMC (HA 90 #1)		V. McK. et al.
	171	FWW1	" LMC		Various
	172	FWW2	" " SMC		Various
	173	FWW3	" " "		Various
	174	FWW4	Red variables "		V. McK. & N.
	175	FWW5	Var's in NGC 1846, 2315		FWW?
Box 270	176	FWW Var.1	Var's in ω Cen, NGC 4833, NGC 7099		FWW et al.
	177	FWW Var.2	Var's in NGC 3201		FWW et al.
	178	FWW Var.3	" " "		FWW et al.
	179	FWW Blk III	Milky Way Bureau, Red Magns		FWW
	180	FWW	Leo I - periods; Vela		FWW
Books in book condition; numbers on front cover	181	11	Variables in ω Cen		E. F. Healand
	182	12	" " "		"
	183	13	" " "		"
	184	17	" " " ; misc var's		"
	185		K Crucis		?
	186		Hercules Cluster		?
	187	2	Messier 5		I. E. Wood
	188		ω Centauri; Eros 2.		
	189	No.1	Measurements of Clusters		E. L. ?
	190	No.2	Discussion of Measures of Clusters		
	191	No.3	Measures of Clusters		
	192	43	Measures Cl. in Per; Obs + Magn.	1903	F. E. Braseh
	193		Work on Mag. Cls. 1924-25	1924-25	L. H. Wilson S. M. Mindes E. F. Sanborn
	194		Var's in Aql & Sct - mostly NA plates	1931-37	

Box 271

Box 272

195 ~~42~~
 196 42
 197
 198 53
 199 ~~53~~
 200
 201
 202 15
 203
 204 IIa
 205
 206 S.G. III
 207 S.G. IV
 208 S.G. VI
 209 S.G. V
 210
 211
 212
 213
 214
 215
 216
 217
 218
 219
 220
 221
 222 A
 223 B
 224 C
 225 D
 226 E
 227 F
 228 G
 229 H
 230 I
 231 J
 232 K
 233 L
 234

Shorthand notes
 Cluster in Perseus, Pos + mag.
 Variables in LMC
 Misc. Variables
 Variables in Car. + Vel
 Measurements at Maria Mitchell
 Work on spectra
 Misc. Var star work
 Tests on 60-in Telescope
 LMC Variables - mags.
 Sequences in SMC
 SA 194-195; SA 197-199
 SA 196
 SA 188-194
 SA 177-182
 Star counts of the LMC
 Bright Variable Star Survey, Field 8
 Measures of Peruvian Pole Star Plates
 VSF Variables SA 16, MWF 208, Anticenter 6 01 + 17.6, 122, 190
 VSF " MSF 299, 305, 679 + 298
 Positions of Variables around LMC
 Sequences in LMC
 Nebulous Objects in MCs
 AM Plate Milky Way Atlas
 Clusters in MCs
 "Milky Way Borders" (publ. in HA 106 #3)
 Positions in Cen
 O-stars; P-Cygni stars
 Spectra - η Car and others
 Spectra
 Spectral Classification - Bright Stars
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1921-26 H. Shapley
 1903 S.E. Breslin
 ~1931? S.F. Missell
 F.W. Wright
 " "
 " "
 1921 H. Shapley
 1921-46 A. Walker
 1924-26
 1931 Nadalin Ross
 A. Ames
 S. Gaposchkin
 "
 "
 "
 M. Miller?
 ?
 ?
 1901 L.R. Ford lays
 A.B. Hearn
 T.K.
 M.W.
 1953 M.S. Matthei
 V. McK. Nail
 ?
 H. Shapley
 V. McK. Nail
 H. Shapley
 J. Sweeney et al.
 A. Walker
 D. Hoffleit
 "
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